

THE OPPORTUNITIES AND ADVERSITIES OF THE ALTERNATIVE DELIVERY MODALITIES IMPLEMENTED IN PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN THE DIVISION OF ISABELA AND ITS IMPACT ON LEARNERS' PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic has brought significant changes to the education sector, particularly with the shift to alternative learning delivery modalities (ADMs). The pandemic forced schools to move away from traditional face-to-face instruction, prompting the Department of Education (DepEd) to implement its Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BELCP) for the 2020-2021 school year. This study, focused on the Division of Isabela, explored school heads' and teachers' perceptions of the opportunities, challenges, and impacts of ADMs such as online, modular, TV-based, and radio-based instruction. Using a descriptive research design, 587 school heads and 1594 teachers participated in a survey covering their profiles, ADM perceptions, and confidence levels. Results indicated that while ADMs provided opportunities for flexible and independent learning, they also presented challenges, particularly with student engagement, tracking progress, and connectivity issues. The study found significant differences in respondents' perceptions based on their age, position, and educational qualifications, with school heads and teachers showing varying levels of confidence in using different ADMs. Ultimately, the study concluded that ADMs were effective in ensuring learning continuity during the pandemic but recommended continuous training and evaluation to further improve their implementation.

Keywords: *Alternative Learning Modality, Learners Performance*

INTRODUCTION

One of the potent issues in our country today is the tremendous change in pedagogical method that was brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic. Accordingly, the education sector is one of the most affected as schools and community learning centers had to forgo of the face-to-face learning engagement of students and teachers. Pursuant to this, SY 2020-2021 ushered the beginning of the so-called "Education in the New Normal." Moreover, the Department of Education has been firm on its stand that "learning must continue." Thus, different modalities have been considered and explored to ascertain that each will best fit students' needs and interests to ensure smooth and seamless learning despite the significant instructional shift.

Subsequently, are other concerns such as budget issues as not all have the resource to purchase gadgets and obtain above-average internet access, students not being able to seek teachers' immediate guidance in difficult classroom lessons and activities or that parents themselves do not have the basic training in navigating apps or online tools utilized in e-classes.

In response to this crisis while guaranteeing learning continuity and assuring the health, safety, and well-being of all learners, teachers, and allied employees, the Department of Education issued DepEd Order No.12 series of 2020, the main goal of which is to establish learning delivery modalities in all levels as embodied in the Learning Continuity Plan (LCP) for the school year 2020-2021. The BE-LCP has likewise been designed with a framework responsive to the "new normal," with the end goal that all citizens must be entitled to quality education at all times as embodied in the 1987 Constitution. Moreover, together with the Department of Education, the Division of Isabela, uses Section 1, article XIV of the 1987 Constitution as its guiding light in effecting classes in the new normal. To wit, Section 1, article XIV states: "The State shall protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels and shall take appropriate steps to make education accessible to all." This is the driving force that directs the Division to steer ways and means to warrant that education carries on while taking into account the health and safety of learners, teachers and others involved in the learning process. The Division furthermore views for improved learning outcomes under the Basic Education Learning Continuity

Research Questions

This study endeavored to find out the perception of school heads and teachers on the alternative learning delivery modalities in the new normal as basis for an enhanced BE-LCP in the Division of Isabela.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents relative to the following:
 - a. Gender
 - b. Age
 - c. Educational Attainment

- d. Length of Service
 - e. Position
 - f. trainings attended on Alternative Delivery Modalities
2. How do school heads and teachers perceive the alternative delivery modalities implemented in terms of:
 - a. Opportunities derived from the different alternative learning delivery modes
 - b. Adversities encountered in these alternative learning delivery modes
 - c. Impact of these alternative learning delivery modes on the learners' performance
 3. Is there a significant difference in the perception of the respondents when grouped according to their profile?
 4. Is there significant difference in the perception of school heads and teachers on the different alternative learning delivery modes?
 5. How confident are the respondents in using the different learning modalities?
 6. Is there a significant difference in the confidence level of the school heads and teachers on the use of the different learning modalities?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used the Descriptive Method with the structured questionnaires as the principal source of data. Calderon (2006) defines descriptive research as a purposive process of gathering, analyzing, classifying, and tabulating data about prevailing conditions, practices, processes, trends, and cause-effect relationships and then making adequate and accurate interpretation about such data with or without or sometimes.

This method is deemed appropriate for this study since it intends to look into some information regarding the respondents, their perception on the Alternative learning delivery modalities in terms of opportunities, adversities and their impact on pupils' performance, and the confidence level of the respondent in the use of different learning modalities.

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted in the public elementary schools in the six legislative districts in the Division of Isabela.

Selection and Description of Respondents

The respondents of the study are 587 public elementary school heads and 1594 public elementary school teachers in the Division of Isabela. They were selected from a total population of 763 school heads and 67880 teachers using stratified sampling. Each

grade level in every school of the six legislative districts was represented in the sample size proportionate to the school population.

Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents per legislative district

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents

Legislative District	School Heads	Teachers	Sample Size of School Heads	Sample Size Teachers
Legislative District 1	138	1337	110	279
Legislative District 2	151	1268	120	274
Legislative District 3	148	1414	114	287
Legislative District 4	92	680	62	234
Legislative District 5	136	1335	102	282
Legislative District 6	98	746	79	238
Total	763	6780	587	1594

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher used a structured questionnaire to gather data needed for the study. The questionnaire has three parts: Part I is intended to draw the school heads and teachers' profile as to sex, age, educational qualification, length of service, alternative delivery mode, position, and trainings attended on

Part II gathered the respondent's perception on the alternative delivery modalities vis-à-vis opportunities of the different alternative learning delivery modes, adversities encountered in these delivery modes and the impact of these on the learners' performance. Responses were based from the scale ranging from 4-Strongly Agree, 3-Agree, 2-Disagree and 1- Strongly Disagree.

The instrument for opportunities of Online learning delivery mode consisting of 20-items was patterned after a study made by Ullah (2018). The items on opportunities for Modular learning delivery mode were patterned after the study of Anzaldo (2021), which consists of 10 items. The opportunities for Television-Based Instruction learning delivery mode were patterned after the study of Mustapha Mohammed, Haroun G.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data gathered in this study were analyzed using the following statistical tools.

Frequency and Percentage Distribution.

This was used to describe the profile of respondents.

Weighted Mean.

This was used to analyze the perception of respondents on the different learning delivery modes in terms of opportunities, adversities, impact on the learners' performance. This was used also to determine the extent of the confidence level of the respondents in using the different learning modalities.

F-Test. This was used to determine the significant differences between the variables as perceive by the School Heads and Teachers. It was used to determine if there is significant difference in the perception of the respondents on the benefits, disadvantages and challenges, and impact on the pupils' performance when grouped according to profile of the different alternative delivery modalities. This was also used to determine the significant difference in the confidence level of the respondents in the use of different learning modalities.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Profile of School Heads and Teachers Respondents

The profile of the school head and teacher-respondents such as sex, age, educational qualification, length of service, position, and trainings attended on Alternative Delivery Mode are presented in the following tables.

Table 2
Gender Profile of School Heads and Teachers

Gender	School Head		Teacher	
	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
Male	247	42.08	182	11.42
Female	340	57.92	1412	88.58
Total	587	100.00	1594	100.00

Table 2 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of school heads and teachers according to gender.

As seen in the table, majority of the respondents are female as shown by the frequency of 340 or 57.92 percent for school heads and 1412 or 88.58 percent for teachers. Data prove that there are more female school heads and teachers than males in the academe. In the study of Regaldo (2017), census findings disclose that in the Philippines, teaching is a woman-dominated profession. There are more female school teachers than male, both in the public elementary and secondary schools.

In addition, Esplada (2010), cites that DepEd records show that 86 percent of the total population of teachers in the Philippines are female.

b. Sex

Table 3
Age Profile of School Heads and Teachers

Age	School Head		Teacher	
	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
20-28	3	0.51	172	10.79
29-37	22	3.75	385	24.15
38-46	141	24.02	572	35.89
47-55	264	44.02	327	20.51
56 and above	157	26.75	138	8.66
Total	587	100.00	1594	100.00

Table 3 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to age. The result show that the age of the respondents ranges from 20 to 56 years old and above.

The data reveals that among the school heads, 264 or 44.97% belong to 47-55 years old age group, 157 or 26.75 percent fall under 56 and above; 141 or 24.02 percent are of age 38-46; 22 or 3.75 percent are in the 29-37 years old age group; three or 0.51 percent are 20-28years old. This implies that majority of the school heads are in the middle ages and the lowest percentage are the millennials.

For the teacher-respondents, 572 or 35.89 percent belong to the age bracket of 38-46; 385 or 24.15 percent are 29-37 years old; 327 or 20.51 percent are of age 47-55; 172 or 10.79 percent are of age 20-28 and 138 or 8.66 percent are 56 years old and above. This implies that majority of the teacher- respondents belong to generation Y who are typically perceived as increasingly familiar with digital or electronic technology.

Findings also show that the group of school heads is generally older than the teachers group.

Table 4
Educational Attainment of School Heads and Teachers

Highest Educational Attainment	School Head		Teacher	
	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
Doctorate Degree	160	27.26	24	1.51
Master and Doctoral Unit	135	23.00	82	5.14

Master's Degree	150	25.55	510	32.00
Baccalaureate Degree with Master's Degree	138	23.51	838	52.57
Baccalaureate Degree	4	0.68	140	8.78
Total	587	100.00	1594	100.00

Table 4 shows reflect the frequency and percentage distribution of teachers and school heads according to their educational qualification. Data shows that there are 160 school head-respondents or 27.26 percent with doctorate degree; 150 or 25.55 percent have finished their masters' degree; 135 or 23 percent have earned doctoral units; 138 or 23.51 percent have masteral units and four or 0.68 percent are baccalaureate degree holders. It can be deduced that the school heads have high educational attainment as shown by the majority of them possessing a doctorate degree or a master's degree.

For teachers' respondents, 838 or 52.57 percent have BS Degree w/ MA units; 510 or 32 percent have a Masters' Degree; 140 or 8.78 percent are Baccalaureate Degree holders; 82 or 5.14 percent have earned doctoral units and 24 or 1.51 percent are doctorate degree holders. There is a compelling need for the elementary teachers to grow professionally and qualify themselves educationally top have an edge for promotion to higher positions.

One of the criteria to qualify for a higher position is to have at least units towards a master's degrees as mandated in DepEd Order no. 39, s. 2007.

The data indicates that School Heads have gone into improving their craft through graduate and post graduate studies. According to them it is one of the requirements in becoming a school head. The teachers on the other hand, have pursued their graduate education to make them more competent and for salary upgrading.

Table 5
Length of Service of School Heads and Teachers

Highest Educational Attainment	School Head		Teacher	
	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
0-5 years	5	0.85	388	24.34
6-11 years	23	3.92	444	27.85
12-17 years	88	14.99	298	18.70
18 – 23 years	142	24.20	201	12.61
24 and above	329	56.04	263	16.50
Total	587	100.00	1594	100.00

Table 5 bares the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to their length of experience. For the school heads, 329 or 56.04 percent have 24 years of experience or more; 142 or 24.20 percent have to 18-23 years of service, 88 or 14.99 percent have served for 12-17 years; 23 or 3.92 percent for 6-11 years; and five or 0.85 percent have served for 0-5 years.

For the teachers' respondents 388 or 24.34 percent have 0-5 years experience; 444 or 27.85 percent have 6-11 years; 298 or 18.70 percent for 12- 17 years; 201 or 12.61 percent have 18-23 years of service and 263 or 16.50 percent have served for 24 years or more.

The data implies that majority of the school heads have stayed long in the service. The reason for staying long in the service is due to retirement benefits and the chances for advancement the Philippine educational system offers. On the other hand, majority of the teachers have shorter stay in the service compared to the school heads.

Resolution No. 070520 dated March 19, 2007 of the Civil Service Commission (CSC), has modified the Qualification Standards (QS) for Head Teachers and Principals in the elementary and secondary schools setting certain number of years of relevant experiences and other criteria an employee must have to qualify for a school head position. A new employee cannot easily be promoted to a school head position without rendering enough years based on the qualification standards.

Table 6
Position Classification of School Heads and Teachers

School Head			Teacher		
Position	<i>f</i>	%	Position	<i>f</i>	%
Head Teacher I	45	7.67	Teacher I	321	20.14
Head Teacher II	4	0.68	Teacher II	45	2.82
Head Teacher III	128	21.81	Teacher III	1088	68.26
Principal I	160	27.26	Master Teacher I	82	5.15
Principal II	129	21.98	Master Teacher II	49	3.07
Principal III	16	2.72	Master Teacher III	4	0.25
Principal IV	5	0.85	Other/LSB/PSB/GIF	5	0.31
Other/TIC/OIC	100	17.03			
	587	100.00		1594	100.00

Table 6 illustrates the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to position classification. There are 160 or 27.26 percent with Principal 1 position; 129 or 21.81 percent hold Principal 11 position; 16 or 2.72 percent are Principal 111 and five or 0.85 percent hold Principal IV position. There are 177 head teachers where 45 or 7.67 percent are Head Teacher I; four or 0.68 percent are Head Teacher II and 128 or 21.81 percent are Head Teacher III. One hundred or 17.03 percent have OIC or TIC designations.

For teachers, 82 or 5.15 percent are MT 1; 49 or 3.07 percent have MT 11 position; four or 0.25 percent are MT 111. For Teacher position, there are 321 or 20.14 percent Teacher I; 45 or 2.82 percent are Teacher II; 1088 or 68.26 percent have Teacher III item and five or 0.31 percent are LSB, PSB or GIP.

It can be viewed that majority of the school heads hold Principal items and for teachers, majority hold Teacher 111 positions. Deped Order no. 42 s. 2017 provides that those aspiring for principal position must pass the qualifying exam for principals conducted by the National Educator's Academy of the Philippines (NEAP) in coordination with the National Education Testing and Research Center (NETRC). Also, a principal aspirant must have an experience of at least five years in aggregate as Head Teacher, Teacher-In-Charge, Master Teacher or Teacher III positions. If not yet a principal passer, employees join assessments for head teacher positions. While teacher-in-charge or school-in-charge are designations appointed by the Schools Division Superintendent but may be replaced whenever there are more qualified employees such as a principal qualifier or a head teacher.

On the other hand, the teachers revealed that they could hardly acquire Master Teacher position because of the rigid requirements and the stiff competition among teachers. The General Guidelines for Master teacher position provides that MT item shall be allotted proportionally on the basis of number of teachers; the number for the division shall likewise be distributed proportionally among all districts.

Table 7
Training Attended by the Respondents on
Alternative Delivery Mode

Trainings Attended	School Head		Teacher	
	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
1-5	333	56.73	1240	77.80
6-10	181	30.84	257	16.12
11 -15	38	6.47	49	3.08
16 and above	35	5.96	48	3.01
Total	587	100.00	1594	100.00

Table 7 reveals the frequency and percentage distribution of school heads and teachers according to trainings attended on Alternative Delivery mode. For school heads, 333 or 56.73 percent have attended 1-5 trainings; 181 or 30.84 percent have 6-10 trainings; 38 or 6.47 percent have attended 11-15 trainings, and 35 or 5.96 percent have 16 or more trainings attended. 16 and above.

On the part of the teacher respondents 1240 or 77.80 percent have attended 1-5 trainings; 257 or 16.12 percent have 6-10 trainings; 49 or 3.08 percent have attended 11-15 trainings, and 48 or 3.01 percent have 16 or more training attended. The data shows that all the school heads and teachers have trainings on Alternative Delivery Modes.

Like the educational attainment, trainings especially on alternative learning delivery is necessary to attain success in education. Trainings give school heads and teachers an opportunity to gain additional and appropriate information that enables them to face various challenges that may affect the furtherance of their schools.

This finding resembles Bagood (2020) findings which highlighted that as front liners in the educational system, they have undergone various training and seminars to be more equipped in delivering better education amid the COVID-19 pandemic. He added that it is a norm of the department to train teachers not just for professional growth but to become ready for unexpected circumstances.

2. School Heads and Teachers' Perception on the Alternative Delivery Modalities

The perception of the school heads and teachers on the alternative delivery mode in terms of opportunities derived from the different alternative learning delivery modes, the adversities encountered and their impact on the learners' performance are presented in the following tables.

a. Opportunities

Table 8
Respondents Perception on the Opportunities Derived from Online Distance Learning (ODL)

Indicators	School Head		Teacher	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Ease of finding information.	3.10	Agree	3.13	Agree
2. Develops the skills of searching for information efficiently.	3.20	Agree	3.17	Agree
3. No limit in distance.	3.20	Agree	3.18	Agree

4. Accessible for learners with disabilities to undergo the learning process.	3.20	Agree	3.12	Agree
5. Amount of time required for the learning process can be decided upon by the learner.	3.27	Strongly Agree	3.12	Agree
6. Ability to manage the time based on the suitability.	3.31	Strongly Agree	3.16	Agree
7. Can be undertaken on an anytime, anywhere basis	3.14	Agree	3.09	Agree
8. Increases level of accessibility.	3.31	Strongly Agree	3.18	Agree
9. The usability and expertise in computer ensures the effectiveness in computer mediated learning.	3.31	Strongly Agree	3.18	Agree
10. Ensures the effectiveness in terms of coping up with missed lectures.	3.18	Agree	3.28	Strongly Agree
11. Productivity of students can be enhanced through online learning to strengthen educational concepts.	3.35	Strongly Agree	3.26	Strongly Agree
12. Economical in terms of time for students and teachers	3.12	Agree	3.21	Agree
13. Ensures the effectiveness for presenting the work in class	3.22	Agree	3.29	Strongly Agree
14. Integrates various types of media thus, quality of teaching and learning can be increased.	3.12	Agree	3.36	Strongly Agree
15. Increase access to education	3.35	Strongly Agree	3.32	Strongly Agree
16. Doing assignments and reading lecture's web notes are easy for students to manage and learn	2.76	Agree	3.25	Strongly Agree
17. Makes learning easier and better than using books/journals in the library.	3.02	Agree	3.17	Agree
18. Makes one become more skillful.	3.29	Strongly Agree	3.32	Strongly Agree

19. Motivates learners through the materials and online activities.	2.96	Agree	3.34	Strongly Agree
20. Learners find it easy to understand and follow the content.	2.92	Agree	3.18	Agree
Mean	3.17	Agree	3.22	Agree

Table 8 presents the respondents' perception on the opportunities of online distance learning modality.

The school heads Strongly Agree that the online distance learning modality allows flexibility in terms of time schedule for students to study as shown in items 5 and 6 with a weighted mean of 3.27 and 3.31, respectively. Also, they strongly agree that online learning increases level of accessibility and usability with a mean of 3.31. They also Strongly Agree that online learning enhances students' productivity (3.26), increases access to education (3.32), and improves students' technology skills (3.32).

On the part of the teachers, they Strongly Agree that online learning ensures the effectiveness for work presentation in class (3.29), motivates learners through online materials (3.34), students' productivity (3.26), increases access to education (3.32), and improves students' technology skills (3.32).

Meanwhile, the school heads and teachers Agree to the other benefits derived from online modality like easy access to information, no time and distance limitations, cost saving, makes learning easier, and learning is made easier for students.

In summary, the respondents Agree that there are opportunities in online learning as reflected by the general weighted mean of 3.17 for school heads and 3.22 for teachers. The findings of this study conforms with that of Cos and Paguia's (2021) findings that one common reason students are interested in online school is the flexibility it offers and they can take classes and study wherever they want, as long as there is an internet connection or materials.

Likewise, it confirms Dana Thomson's (2010) findings in her study that emphasized the significance and appeal of flexibility and expanded opportunity for students enrolled in online courses and Yu's (2006) claim that found positive attitudes of students toward online learning because of the feasibility and new ways of learning.

Table 9 reflects the respondents' perception on the opportunities of modular distance learning.

The school heads and teachers both Strongly Agree that modular distance learning allows learners to seek help from parents, friends and relatives as shown by the weighted mean of 3.40 and 3.31, respectively. Both also Agree that modular learning is more flexible than other approaches in teaching, makes teachers more comfortable to teach

using his/her own modules, makes pupils more active and self-directed, helps the pupils express their ideas, allows pupils to manage their time in answering all the activities, gives pupils much time for self-meditation and self-reflection and allows pupils to study without disturbing their normal activities and responsibilities.

Table 9
Respondents' Perception on the Benefits of
Modular Distance Learning Modality

Indicators	School Head		Teacher	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Helps teachers to explore more in teaching.	3.31	Strongly Agree	3.22	Agree
2. More flexible than other approaches in teaching.	3.15	Agree	3.12	Agree
3. Makes teachers more comfortable to teach using his/her own modules	2.96	Agree	2.98	Agree
4. Gives the learners a lot of time to answer the activities.	3.31	Strongly Agree	3.23	Agree
5. Allow pupils to be guided by friends, parents and relatives on their activities.	3.40	Strongly Agree	3.31	Strongly
6. Makes pupils more active and self-directed.	2.93	Agree	2.91	Agree
7. Helps the pupils express their ideas.	2.90	Agree	2.95	Agree
8. Allows pupils to manage their time in answering all the activities, reading, lectures and so on.	3.13	Agree	3.14	Agree
9. Gives pupils much time for self-meditation and self-reflection.	3.08	Agree	3.13	Agree
10. Allows pupils to study without disturbing the normal activities and responsibilities	3.09	Agree	3.06	Agree
Mean	3.13	Agree	3.10	Agree

The data implies that both the school heads and teachers agree that modular learning has its own benefits as shown by the overall mean value of 3.13 and 3.10.

The family member, relatives and friends of the learners play a vital role in education today. Most students cannot answer their modules independently, that is why they badly need the assistance of others.

This is supported by Dangle and Sumaoang's (2021) claim that most of the students cannot answer all their modules independently, hence they badly need the assistance of others.

Similarly, Kwatubana and Makhalemele (2018) also found out that having parents active in their children's education is beneficial since it increases academic achievement. Students become more focused on their studies.

Furthermore, Manlove and David 16 (1985) also affirm that modular teaching helps each student to think for himself and allowing the individuality to each learner which helps in developing many notable and self-reliant characters, and in much more modern ways pupils enjoy periods in which they pursue their interests and satisfy their curiosities.

Table 10
Respondents' Perception on the Benefits of Television-Based
Instruction (TBI) Learning Modality

Indicators	School Head		Teacher	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. The medium is familiar since most people watch television.	2.50	Agree	3.11	Agree
2. Allowing concepts to be illustrated through visual stimulation.	3.17	Agree	3.05	Agree
3. Effective way for introducing, summarizing, and reviewing concepts.	3.17	Agree	3.11	Agree
4. The lessons are repeated in different schedules.	2.83	Agree	2.24	Agree
5. Allows students to explore new environments.	3.33	Strongly Agree	3.11	Agree
6. Provision of broader student accessibility to educational opportunities.	2.83	Agree	2.95	Agree

7. Copies of taped/video materials can be made available to students for review.	3.00	Agree	2.95	Agree
8. Widely available in rural areas.	3.17	Agree	3.00	Agree
9. Helps to provide knowledge and information in a more direct and concrete form.	3.17	Agree	3.05	Agree
10. Greater students benefit the more the medium is used.	3.50	Strongly Agree	3.00	Agree
Mean	3.07	Agree	3.01	Agree

The opportunities in TBI learning modality as perceived by the respondents are reflected in Table 10.

Data shows that both the school heads and teachers agree that TBI as a learning modality illustrates concepts through visual stimulation, introduces, summarizes, and reviews concepts effectively, lessons can be repeated in different schedules, provides them broader accessibility to educational opportunities, copies of taped/video materials can be made available to students for review, helps to provide knowledge and information in a more direct and concrete form and is widely available in rural areas.

Meanwhile, the school heads Strongly Agree that TBI allows learners to explore new environments and the more the medium is used, the greater students benefit while the teachers Agree to these. It is evident that generally, the respondents perceive the Television- Based Instruction to be an important learning platform.

This findings relate to that of Emerald (2021) that educational television is an excellent means of reinforcing a knowledge base, promoting student interest and engagement, and embraces a wider scope of learning styles than traditional teaching. Likewise, Sen (2021) , also bares some opportunities of Television-Based Instruction as follows: broadens and enriches the classroom learning experiences of the students, creates genuine interest in the topic or the subject that is being taught, evaluates the quality of classroom teaching process, provides a wide variety of experiences that are quite different from the routine classroom-instruction, stimulates less passive slow learners by developing a more critical approach in them, and provides opportunity to learn, to create productions that can improve students ability to communicate.

Table 11 shows the opportunities derived from Radio-Based Instruction Learning Mode as perceived by the school heads and teachers. The table reveals that the school heads and teachers unanimously *agree* that the RBI as a learning modality can be used anywhere with or without electricity, it is easy to access by all students regardless of their age or status, teaches students a new and possibly job-related skill, allows students to work together to complete a project, it is a convenient, easy and economical way of getting ideas and various views from expert, and provides examples of good and bad speeches.

Table 11
 Respondents' Perception of the on the Opportunities of
 Radio-Based Instruction (RBI) Learning Mode

Indicators	School Head		Teacher	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Often used anywhere with or without electricity.	3.02	Agree	3.04	Agree
2. Easy enough to access by all students regardless of their age or status.	2.97	Agree	3.11	Agree
3. Helps the school and teachers to supplement learning and to give different strategies for diverse learners.	3.25	Strongly Agree	3.24	Agree
4. Teaches students a new and possibly job- related skill.	3.12	Agree	3.13	Agree
5. Helps create better ways of learning.	3.14	Agree	3.29	Strongly Agree
6. Working together to complete a project.	3.23	Agree	3.22	Agree
7. Convenient, easy and economical way of getting ideas and various views from expert.	3.15	Agree	3.24	Agree
8. Provide examples of good and bad speeches.	3.09	Agree	3.22	Agree
9. Provide vicarious experiences with travel and daily chores to the listeners.	3.25	Strongly Agree	3.23	Agree
10. Adaptable to either large or small audience in widely separated areas.	3.32	Strongly Agree	3.16	Agree
Mean	3.15	Agree	3.19	Agree

On the other hand, the school heads **Strongly Agree** while teachers **Agree** that the RBI helps the school and teachers to supplement learning and to give different strategies for diverse learners, provides vicarious experiences with travel and daily chores to the listeners and is adaptable to either large or small audience in widely separated areas.

In general, the respondents agree that RBI as a delivery mode has its benefits as reflected in the general weighted mean of 3.15 for school heads and 3.19 for teacher. Arbutante (2020) confirms the findings of the present study in his statement that RBI has impacted the lives of learners in so many different ways. It provided learning opportunities to learners who are unable to attend face to face sessions such as those who are working or living in remote areas, it was successful in expanding access and quality of distance education.

b. Adversities

Table 12
Respondents' Perception of the on the Adversities
of Online Distance (ODL) Learning Modality

Indicators	School Head		Teacher	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Difficult to reach students in remote areas	2.80	Agree	2.71	Agree
2. Difficult to motivate students.	2.80	Agree	2.82	Agree
3. Challenges are experience in tracking student's progress	2.69	Agree	2.82	Agree
4. Problem of electricity/Internet connectivity	2.73	Agree	2.70	Agree
5. Lack of technical/ Software knowledge	2.90	Agree	2.68	Agree
6. Require more time in preparing course content	2.73	Agree	2.63	Agree
7. Online learners are not motivated in this mode	2.65	Agree	2.50	Agree
8. Difficult to teach numerical subject through online mode.	2.76	Agree	2.59	Agree
9. Difficult in monitoring discipline	2.51	Agree	2.72	Agree
10. Attention span is short	2.94	Agree	2.59	Agree
11. Less interaction among teachers and learners to instructional materials	2.53	Agree	2.76	Agree
12. Limited variety of online activities	2.80	Agree	2.63	Agree

13. Difficulty in following the schedule	2.82	Agree	2.67	Agree
14. Lack of clarification in timely manner	2.67	Agree	2.68	Agree
15. Lack of experience on the part of teachers to deal with online learning.	2.80	Agree	2.62	Agree
Mean	2.74	Agree	3.19	Agree

Table 12 presents the perceived adversities of the online distance learning modality.

Based on the results, the school heads and teachers both Agree on the challenges encountered in online learning as reflected in the general weighted mean of 2.74 and 2.68, respectively. These adversities include the following: difficult to reach students in remote areas where there is no internet connectivity, students who are not technologically literate, have no gadgets and have short span of attention are difficult to motivate, difficulty on the part of teachers who are not technology inclined, difficulty in tracking student's progress and monitoring students' discipline, require more time for teachers in preparing the course content, difficulty to teach numerical subject through online mode, and there is less interaction between teacher and learners, among learners and learners to instructional materials, limited variety of online activities, and difficulty in following the class schedule.

Difficulty of tracking students' progress corroborates the findings of Guangul (2020) that one of the challenges identified in remote assessment were academic dishonesty, coverage of learning outcomes, and commitment of students to submit assessments on which teachers are not sure whether the students are the ones who do the activities.

Savenye's (2020) claim that maintaining motivation in an online course is yet another challenge that online learners face and students lack of independence and self-motivation also confirms the findings of the present study.

Continuing with the exploration of internal factors affecting students' attitudes towards online education, it would appear that one's self-discipline and drive will also play a role. A student lacking motivation may find it difficult to stay focused while completing online assignments. Smart and Cappel (2006) supports this belief as students who were interested in the material or identified with it demonstrated a higher level of motivation. Additionally, disinterest and distraction could explain some students' negative attitudes. Golladay, et.al. (2000) have also shown that learning in an online environment requires a significant amount of discipline and self-motivation. This is particularly true where the online units are completed as independent, self-study units, as opposed to users interacting as part of a community of online users.

Table 13
 Respondents' Perception on the Adversities of
 Modular Distance Learning Modality

Indicators	School Head		Teacher	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Time consuming	3.14	Agree	3.23	Agree
2. Lack of printing materials/scarcity of supplies.	3.09	Agree	3.12	Agree
3. Insufficient time and assistance in printing the modules	2.92	Agree	2.97	Agree
4. Some students get their modules late	3.04	Agree	3.22	Agree
5. Transaction system between parent and teacher is not really followed	3.11	Agree	3.12	Agree
6. Inactive contact numbers of learners	3.05	Agree	2.97	Agree
7. Students/parents with no contact numbers and/internet connection are difficult to contact	3.19	Agree	3.26	Strongly Agree
8. Difficulty in validating students' performance	3.21	Agree	3.35	Strongly Agree
9. Personal monitoring may cause health risks	2.83	Agree	2.92	Agree
10. Hard to monitor due to limited face to face transaction	2.98	Agree	2.95	Agree
11. Students' failure to follow the schedule set for the submission of modules	3.08	Agree	3.20	Agree
12. Submission of incomplete answers is observed	3.24	Agree	3.15	Agree
13. Unidentified answer sheets of students	2.84	Agree	3.04	Agree
14. Not all students submit the answered modules	3.02	Agree	3.27	Strongly Agree

15. Modules with no answers/ incomplete answers.	3.00	Agree	3.35	Strongly Agree
16. Answer sheets with no names	2.82	Agree	2.92	Agree
17. Limited time in checking due to other tasks	2.86	Agree	2.96	Agree
18. Students get scores below the passing rate	2.81	Agree	3.20	Agree
19. Not legible handwriting of a student	3.03	Agree	3.15	Agree
20. Copying of answer key is observed and obvious	3.22	Agree	3.05	Agree
Mean	3.02	Agree	3.19	Agree

Table 13 presents the adversities of Modular Distance Learning modality as experienced by the respondents.

It is noted that school heads and teachers both Agree on the adversities encountered in Modular learning with overall weighted means of 3.02 and 3.12 respectively.

Data shows that the modular distance learning modality is time consuming in terms of preparation and printing of modules. Transaction system between parent and teacher is not really followed, there is difficulty in the distribution and retrieval of modules and there is lack of printing materials for the modules.

Findings further reveal that school heads agree that students and parents with no contact numbers and/internet connection are difficult to contact, validating students' performance is difficult, and not all students submit the answered modules while the teachers Strongly Agree to these.

Due to incomplete answers of students in their modules and slow submission of modules, teachers need to conduct personal monitoring despite of the restrictions brought by the pandemic. Findings of the present study is supported Castroverde and Acala (2021) findings that teachers encountered different challenges in the implementation of modular distance learning modality. These challenges include planning and preparation of the modules by the teacher; delivering, collecting, monitoring of students' outputs, checking and evaluating student's outputs, as well as on how they provide feedback to students.

Table 14
 Respondents' Perception on the Adversities of Television-Based
 Instruction (TBI) Learning Modality

Indicators	School Head		Teacher	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. There is absence of learner participation during the program	3.00	Agree	3.21	Agree
2. The program cannot be adapted to individual learners.	3.00	Agree	3.16	Agree
3. There is dissimilarity in the intellectual background of the learners and the TV program does not cater to it.	3.00	Agree	3.26	Strongly Agree
4. The class teacher has no control over the pace of development of a TV lesson.	3.33	Strongly Agree	3.11	Agree
5. Interruptions and distractions at the receiving end can seriously impair the effectiveness of lesson.	3.00	Agree	3.00	Agree
6. Lack of continuing contact and interaction between the teacher and the students	3.00	Agree	3.05	Agree
7. Little or no opportunity for questions and feedback`	2.67	Agree	3.32	Strongly Agree
8. Some courses are technically aesthetic but lacking in substance	3.50	Strong Agree	3.32	Strongly Agree
9. Delay in getting response from lectures in substance	2.50	Agree	3.16	Agree
10. Different time zones affect synchronous sessions	3.50	Strongly Agree	2.89	Agree
Mean	3.05	Agree	3.15	Agree

The adversities of Television- Based Instruction Learning modality as experienced by the respondents are shown in Table 14. The TV program, as perceived by the school heads and teachers cannot be adapted to individual learners and there is dissimilarity in the intellectual background of the learners which the TV program does not cater to. Also, some learners are absent during the airing of the TV program. The respondents also both

agree that there are interruptions and distractions at the receiving end which can seriously impair the effectiveness of a lesson and there is lack of continuing contact and interaction between the teacher and the student. Also, there is delay in getting response from lecturers.

On one hand, the school heads Strongly Agree and teachers Agree that the class teacher has no control over the pace of development of a TV lesson and different time zones affect synchronous sessions. Furthermore, both respondents Strongly Agree that some courses are technically aesthetic but lacking in substance.

The findings of this study is similar to that of Sen (2021) that learners may engage in day dreaming, during the airing of the program because of no individual contact no further action is possible other than viewing and listening and there is absence of learner participation during the program. Her findings further reveals the TBI is a one-way communication, and the TV program cannot be adapted to individual learners. Sen (2021) also found that there is dissimilarity in the intellectual background of the learners and the TV program does not cater to it and the lesson timings are inflexible and sometimes inconvenient. In TBI, the class teacher has no control over the pace of development of a TV lesson and it is difficult to take account of variation in attainment and ability within an age group; interruptions and distractions at the receiving end seriously impair the effectiveness of a lesson, and the effectiveness of any transmitted aid is limited to the range of the transmitter.

Table 15
Respondents' Perception on the Adversities of Radio-Based Instruction Learning Modality

Indicators	School Head		Teacher	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Teachers are trapped with limited time to address individual student difficulties during the programming	2.80	Agree	2.93	Agree
2. There is no interaction with broadcast programs since there is no explicit response from students, it is difficult to know how effective the program is.	3.06	Agree	2.95	Agree
3. Radio broadcast follow a prearranged schedule, to which learners have to adjust, with little timetable flexibility for teachers.	3.02	Agree	2.98	Agree

4. Radio broadcast is restricted to the audio dimension of knowledge.	2.85	Agree	2.90	Agree
5. Teachers lack the skill to produce high quality educational radio programs.	2.82	Agree	2.74	Agree
6. Students have no control over the pace and time of broadcasts.	2.85	Agree	2.90	Agree
7. Non-availability of educational content in audio formats.	2.72	Agree	2.83	Agree
8. Difficulty to produce content in quantity and quality in a short time.	2.85	Agree	2.85	Agree
9. There is a need for communication and collaboration between education specialists and the professionals of the audio sector to produce educational program.	2.97	Agree	2.98	Agree
10. Lack of the knowhow and expertise in monitoring and evaluation of learning.	2.80	Agree	2.90	Agree
Mean	2.87	Agree	2.90	Agree

Table 15 reflects the adversities of Radio- Based Instruction (TBI) learning modality as perceived by the respondents.

Based on the results, the school heads and teachers Agree to all adversity indicators for TBI as reflected in the overall mean of 2.87 for school heads and 2.90 for teachers.

The respondents agree that in RBI, teachers are trapped with limited time to address individual student difficulties during the programming. Also, here is no interaction with broadcast programs since there is no explicit response from students, it is difficult to know how effective the program is and radio broadcast follow a prearranged schedule, to which learners have to adjust, with little timetable flexibility for teachers. Further, the respondents agree that radio broadcast is restricted to the audio dimension of knowledge, teachers lack the skill to produce high quality educational radio programs and students have no control over the pace and time of broadcasts. Moreover, there are no available educational content in audio formats and it is difficult to produce content in quantity and

quality in a short time and there is a need for communication and collaboration between education specialists and the professionals of the audio sector to produce educational program.

In Ali (2016) study, he found out that Radio based Instruction can be impersonal and students listening for long to a voice from a box can lose interest quickly and normally there is no student feedback which is spontaneous although the use of listening groups and distance education courses can help to overcome this disadvantage. He further found out that radio programs cannot provide visual help and therefore there is a limitation on the variety of subjects which can be taught. Radio program reception, according to him can be interrupted thus causing loss of continuity. Also, lengthy regular radio programs unsupported in other ways cause difficulties of self-discipline among students and because radio programs are beamed to a large audience and "anybody" may be listening in, there is often an initial reluctance on the part of tutors who have had little experience of the medium to commit themselves to the radio.

c. Impact

Table 16
Respondents' Perception on the Impact of Online Distance Learning Modality on Learners' Performance

Indicators	School Head		Teacher	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Learners show progress toward course objectives	3.10	Agree	3.13	Agree
2. Learners interest in each subject increased	3.02	Agree	3.18	Agree
3. Learners are able to think independently about the subject matter	3.08	Agree	3.18	Agree
4. Learners are actively involved in learning	3.24	Agree	3.32	Strongly Agree
5. Learners has put effort in course	3.14	Agree	3.16	Agree
6. Learners manages "study time" effectively and easily complete assignments on time	3.24	Agree	3.20	Agree
7. Educational needs of the learners are met in the online learning delivery mode.	3.20	Agree	3.32	Strongly Agree

8. Makes the communication between teacher and Learners easier	3.31	Strongly Agree	3.38	Strong Agree
9. Help learners become more familiar with the course	3.29	Agree	3.28	Agree
10. Learners have more positive attitude towards online learning modality	3.12	Agree	3.18	Agree
Mean	3.18	Agree	3.23	Agree

Table 16 presents the respondents' perception on the impact of online distance learning modality on learners' performance.

The data reveals that the school heads and teachers Strongly Agree that through ODL communication between teacher and learners is easier and the learners became more familiar with the course. Both respondents also Agree that learners show progress toward course objectives and learners interest in each subject increased. Furthermore, learners are able to think independently about the subject matter and are actively involved in learning. Learners have also put effort in their study course and manage "study time" effectively and easily complete assignments on time

The impact of ODL on students' performance in the present study is confirmed in Sanders (2002) study that ODL revealed progressive impact on the learning of students with reference to their problem-solving approach and development of critical thinking abilities. Similarly, Paris (2004) also revealed better response of students in online learning program.

Table 17
Respondents' Perception on the Impact of Modular Distance Learning Modality on Learners' Performance

Indicators	School Head		Teacher	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Learners can comprehend instructions and learn on their own with their parents' guidance.	3.15	Agree	3.22	Agree
2. Learners have increased understanding of the lesson	3.08	Agree	3.09	Agree
3. Learners acquire necessary knowledge from the module	3.10	Agree	2.92	Agree

4. Learners engagement and interest levels remain as instructions from the module are easy to grasp.	3.04	Agree	3.16	Agree
5. Learners understand completely the content of the module	3.10	Agree	3.22	Agree
6. Learners are interested to learn more and know more.	3.04	Agree	2.85	Agree
7. Learners have a good study strategy and high study effort	2.29	Agree	2.89	Agree
8. Learners are highly motivated to learn the topics presented by teachers	3.00	Agree	3.07	Agree
9. Learners are persistent to pursue learning even when faced by obstacles during the teaching learning process	3.02	Agree	3.01	Agree
10. Learners have the drive to reach out their learning goals	3.12	Agree	3.01	Agree
Mean	3.06	Agree	3.04	Agree

The respondents' perception on the impact of modular distance learning modality on learners' performance is shown in Table 17.

Results show the school heads and teacher respondents agree that the modular distance learning as a modality has impacted on students' performance. They agree that the learners have increased understanding of the lesson, have acquired added knowledge from the module and their engagement and interest levels is sustained as instructions from the module are easy to grasp and eager to learn more and know more.

The findings of the present study corroborate Epstein (2010) findings that students' academic achievement is enhanced when schools, families, and communities work together and support each other.

Table 18 presents the impact of Television-Based Instruction learning modality on the learners' performance as perceived by the school heads and teachers.

The table shows that both school heads and teachers agree to all the impact indicators except for the item *Learners comprehension and discussion of content is enhanced* where the teachers "Strongly Agreed" while the school heads agreed. Television-Based Instruction, according to the respondents has the following impact on students; performance: learners comprehension and discussion of content is enhanced; a common base of knowledge is developed among learners; learners have increased

motivation and enthusiasm for learning; learners' ability to recall and extract abstract problem-solving skills is improved.

Table 18
 Respondents' Perception on the Impact of Television-Based Instruction Learning Modality on Learners' Performance

Indicators	School Head		Teacher	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Learners' comprehension and discussion of content enhanced.	3.17	Agree	3.26	Strongly Agree
2. Aids in the development of a common base of knowledge among learners.	2.67	Agree	2.79	Agree
3. Learners have increased motivation and enthusiasm for learning.	3.00	Agree	2.95	Agree
4. Improve children ability to recall story plots and extract abstract problem-solving skills.	2.83	Agree	3.05	Agree
5. Engaged children in practicing newly learned skills.	3.17	Agree	2.58	Agree
Mean	2.97	Agree	2.93	Agree

Haroun (2017) revealed that there can no longer be any doubt that students learnt efficiently from instructional television.

Table 19 reflects the impact of Radio-Based Instruction learning modality on learners' performance.

Results show that the school heads and teacher respondents Agree that RBI has provided learners with curriculum-aligned content of a consistent standard and has improved learners' skill. Also, RBI, according to the respondents has progressively increased learners achievement and have helped learners deal with difficult learning concepts. This is reflected in the overall mean of 3.12 for school heads and 3.19 for teachers.

Table 19
 Respondents' Perception on the Impact of Radio-Based Instruction
 Learning Modality on Learners' Performance

Indicators	School Head		Teacher	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Provide learners with curriculum-aligned content of a consistent standard.	3.00	Agree	3.23	Agree
2. Helps improve learners' skill.	3.23	Agree	3.20	Agree
3. Learners achievement has increased progressively.	3.11	Agree	3.12	Agree
4. Excellent tool for learners to deal with difficult learning concepts.	3.17	Agree	3.24	Agree
5. Help Learners to be more familiar with the course.	3.09	Agree	3.13	Agree
Mean	3.12	Agree	3.19	Agree

Odera as cited by Elliot and Lashley (2017), claim that broadcast helps to provide opportunity to provide stimulating and rehearsing communicative situation to be encountered outside the primary classroom. It is a skilled behavior which is only effective when two or more people are involved and more so in using audio or face to face communication, since the introduction of school radio broadcast, the emphasis has been on singing along with the songs played by the classroom teacher who is expected to be a facilitator doing only what is directed by the radio teacher. The rationale is that learners benefit from listening to the well-researched mathematics lessons and learn the mathematical operations taught by prepared radio presenters.

Russell et al., as cited by Elliot and Lashley (2017), also noted the value of radio technology and recommended its use to increase and improve learner's imagination and listening skills. They recognized the importance of radio as a medium that relies on a single sense (hearing) and with which listening is the only method of learn

9. Is there a significant difference in the perception of the respondents when grouped according to their profile?

a. School Heads
a.1 Opportunities
a.1.1 Sex

Table 20
 Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the
 School Heads on the Opportunities Derived from the
 Different Distance Learning Modalities When
 Grouped According of Sex

School Heads' Perception on the Opportunities in the DLMS and Sex	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
1. Online Distance Learning	0.4991	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
2. Modular Distance Learning	0.7882	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
3. Excellent tool for learners to deal with difficult learning concepts.	0.3914	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
4. Help Learners to be more familiar with the course.	0.3914	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Mean	0.1597	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant

Table 20 presents the results of the test significant difference in the perception of the school heads on the opportunities derived from the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to their sex.

The results show that the significance of F or P-values are greater than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at 0.05 level of significance meaning there is no significance difference in the perception of the school heads on the opportunities of the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to sex. It implies that the male school heads and the female school heads have similar perceptions on the opportunities derived from online and modular learning modalities, and television and radio-based instruction.

According to Moses (2016) ,the gender of the respondents does not have a relation to their level of instructional modalities awareness. Gender might not be a vial factor in clarifying what aspects of forthcoming teachers are enticed to teaching.

a.1.2 Age

Table 21
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the School Heads on the Opportunities Derived from the Different Distance Learning Modalities When Grouped According Age

School Heads' Age and the Opportunities on the following learning modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	0.812	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Modular Distance Learning	6.3386×10^{23}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	0.0142	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	4.2116×10^{-18}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant

The result of the test of significant difference in the perception of the school heads on the opportunities derived from the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to age are presented in Table 21.

Data reveals that the computed P-values are less 0.05 except for online distance learning. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 significance level. Therefore, there is significant difference in the perception of the school heads on the opportunities of modular distance learning, television and radio-based instruction when grouped according to their age.

The researcher found out that the school heads who belong to the age bracket 20-28 have better perception on the opportunities of modular learning, while those in under the age group of 38-46 have better perception on the opportunities derived from television-based instruction, and those of age 29-37, on radio-based instruction.

On the other hand, there is no significant difference in their perception on the benefits derived from online learning as shown by the computed P-value which is greater than 0.05 level of significance. This means that they have similar perceptions on the opportunities derived from online learning.

a.1.3 Educational Attainment

Table 22
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the School Heads on the Opportunities Derived from the Different Distance Learning Modalities When Grouped According to Their Educational Attainment

School Heads' Educational Attainment and the Opportunities on the following learning modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	5.0674×10^{-16}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	1.3209×10^{-20}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	0.0142	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	3.5521×10^{-21}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant

Table 22 disclose the results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the school heads on the benefits of the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to their educational attainment.

It is evident from the results that the P-values are less than 0.05. For this reason, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. This means that there is significant difference in the perception of the school heads on the benefits of the different alternative learning modes when grouped according to their educational qualification. Findings show that the school heads with masters' degree perceive better the benefits of online and modular learning delivery modes, while those with MA units perceive better the benefits of television based instruction, and those with doctorate degree perceive the radio based learning delivery mode as more beneficial.

a.1.4 Length of Service

The result of the test of significance difference in the perception of the school heads on the benefits of the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to their length of service are disclosed in Table 23.

It reflects that the test of significant difference resulted to a P-values that are less than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the school head significantly vary in their perception on the benefits of the different alternative leaning delivery modes when grouped according to their length of service. The researcher further noted that school heads who have been in the service. The researcher further

noted that school heads who have been in the service for 18-23 years perceive online distance learning to be more beneficial while those whose length of service is 0-5 years consider modular learning as more beneficial. Whereas, those who have serve for 6-11 years are more on television based instruction, and those who have work experience for 12-17 years perceive better the opportunities of radio based instruction.

Table 23
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the School Heads on the Opportunities Derived from the Different Distance Learning Modalities When Grouped According to Their Length of Service

School Heads' Length of Service and the Opportunities on the following learning modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	6.6921×10^{-18}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	2.7692×10^{-16}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	0.0082	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	0.0071	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant

a.1.5 Position

Table 24
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the School Heads on the Benefits of the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes When Grouped According to Position

School Heads' Position and the Opportunities on the following learning modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	1.9991×10^{-23}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	2.047×10^{-17}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	0.0075	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant

Radio-Based Instruction	3.8087×10^{-15}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
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Table 24 exhibits the results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the school heads on the benefits of the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to their position.

The results yielded P-values that are less than 0.05 which means the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is significant difference in the perception of the school heads on the benefits of the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to their position. The Head Teachers 3 and Principals 2 find online learning delivery mode most beneficial, while Head Teachers 2 are more on modular. Likewise, the Head Teachers 3 more on radio based instruction.

a.1.6 Trainings attended on Alternative Delivery Modes

Table 25
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the School Heads on the Opportunities of the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes when Grouped According to Their Trainings

School Heads Trainings attended on Alternative Delivery Modes and the Opportunities on the following learning modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	6.0663×10^{-23}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	0.0015	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	0.0190	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	0.0009	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant

The results of significant difference in the perception of the school heads on the opportunities of the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to the trainings attended on alternative delivery mode are exhibited in Table 25.

It reveals that the computed P-values are less than 0.05. For this reason, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 significance level meaning, there is significant difference in the perception of the school heads on the opportunities of the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to their trainings on alternative delivery mode. As indicated by the mean in Appendix C, those school heads with 6-10 times attendance to trainings on alternative delivery mode have better perception of the opportunities on

online and radio based learning delivery modes, while those with 1-5 and 11-15 attendance find more beneficial the modular and television based as alternative learning delivery modes, respectively.

The result of this study is supported by the study of Holmes and Nielson as cited by Halili and Villajuan (2021) that school administrators and teachers need training to receive some form of planned learning experiences because they are responsible for their staff and their pupils, the learning process within their schools, and the premises in which this process takes place. Relevant trainings for teachers or employees should be part of professional development. These should include knowledge, skills and competencies. Attendance to such relevant trainings enables them to adapt to changes and become more creative members of the educational institutions. These trainings are necessary because they lead their clientele who also possesses talents, values, and attitudes like them.

a.2 Adversities

a.2.1 Gender

Table 26
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the School Heads on the Adversities Encountered in the Different Distance Learning Modalities When Grouped According to Their Gender

School Heads Gender Adversities Encountered on the following learning modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	0.0081	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	0.0430	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	0.6586	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	0.3587	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant

Table 26 presents the results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the school heads on the adversities encountered in the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to their gender.

The results show that the P-values are less than 0.05 for online and modular distance learning. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is significant difference in the perception of the school heads on the adversities encountered in online and modular distance learning when grouped according

to their gender. It implies that the male school heads differ in their perception of the adversities encountered along these two alternative learning delivery modes from that of the female school heads. Findings reveal that the female school heads encountered more adversities in online distance learning than their male counterpart and the male school heads experience more adversities in modular learning mode.

There is no significant difference, however, in the adversities encountered by the school heads in television and radio based instruction when grouped according to their gender. This is reflected in the computed P values which are greater than 0.05 significance level.

a.2.2 Age

Table 27
Results of the test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the School Heads on the Adversities Encountered in the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes When Grouped According to Their Age

School Heads Age Adversities Encountered on the following learning modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	0.0007	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	4.161×10^{-47}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	0.0114	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	1.1298×10^{-11}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the school heads on the adversities encountered in the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to their age are presented in Table 27.

Data shows that the computed P-values are less than 0.05 which signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the school heads significantly differ in the adversities they encountered in the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to their age. It shows that school heads who belong to age bracket of 20-28 encountered more adversities on online and modular learning delivery modes, while those of 38-46 and 29-37 years old have more adversities on television and radio based learning modes.

a.2.3 Educational Attainment

Table 28

Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the School Heads on the Adversities Encountered in the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes When Grouped According to Their Educational Attainment

School Heads Educational Attainment & Challenges Encountered on the following learning modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	1.017×10^{-13}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	1.0512×10^{-56}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	0.0114	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	0.4528	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant

Table 28 discloses the results of the test of significant difference in the perceived adversities encountered in the different alternative learning delivery modes by school heads when grouped according to their educational attainment.

The results show that the computed P-values are less than 0.05. for online, modular and TV-based instruction. For this reason, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 significance level, thus, there is significant difference in the adversities encountered by school heads on online and modular distance and television based instruction when grouped according to their educational qualification. The study shows that the school heads with Ph.D. units encounter more adversities both on online and modular learning modalities, while those with MA units had more adversities on television- based learning mode.

On the other hand, the school heads do not significantly differ in the adversities encountered in radio based instruction when grouped according to their educational attainment as shown by the computed P-value which is greater than the significance level.

a.2.4 Length of Service

The results of significant difference in the school heads' perceived adversities encountered in the different learning modalities when grouped according to their length of service are disclosed in Table 29.

It is evident from the results that the computed P-values are less than 0.05, hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. This means that there is significance difference in the adversities encountered by the school heads in the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to their length of service. School heads who are younger in the service encounter more adversities both in online and modular instruction while those who are older in the service have more adversities on television and radio-based instruction.

Table 29
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the School Heads on the Adversities Encountered in the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes When Grouped According to Their Length of Service

School Heads Length of Service Adversities Encountered on the following learning modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	1.8646×10^{-15}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	8.3563×10^{-13}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	0.0025	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	2.9698×10^{-18}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant

a.2.5 Position

Table 30
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the School Heads on the Adversities Encountered in the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes When Grouped According to Their Position

School Heads Length of Service Adversities Encountered on the following learning modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	2.0045×10^{-22}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	8.448×10^{-10}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant

Television-Based Instruction	0.0342	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	5.6877x10 ⁻¹⁵	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant

Table 30 exhibits the results of the test of significant difference in the perceived adversities encountered by the school heads on the four learning modalities when grouped according to their position.

It can be gleaned from the results that the computed P-values are less than 0.05 which signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is significance difference in the adversities encountered by the school heads in the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to their position. Findings show that those with Principal 1 position encounter more adversities both in online and television-based instruction and those with a position of Head Teacher 1 and Principal 3 experience more adversities in modular and radio based instruction.

a.2.6 Trainings attended on Alternative Delivery Mode

Table 31

Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Adversities Encountered by the School Heads in the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes When Grouped According to Trainings Attended

School Heads Trainings attended on Alternative Delivery mode Adversities Encountered on the following learning modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	4.9142 x 10 ⁻²⁰	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	4.6527x10 ⁻⁸⁶	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	0.8010	P>0.05	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	0.3177	P>0.05	Accept H ₀	Not Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the school heads' adversities encountered in the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to their trainings attended on alternative delivery mode are exhibited in Table 31.

The Test of significant difference yielded a P-values that is less than 0.05 for online and modular distance learning. For this reason, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05

significance level, meaning there is significant difference in the adversities encountered by the school heads in online and modular distance learning when grouped according to the trainings they have attended on alternative delivery mode. It shows that the school heads who attended trainings for 1-5 times encounter more adversities in online instruction while those who have attended six or more trainings find more difficulty in modular instruction. This findings is supported by the study of Ancheta (2021) which reveals that seminars on educational management and other matters related to education are critical because they provide the information skills, competencies, and desired values and attitudes of school personnel both ow and the future especially those who are considered neophytes in the profession.

However, no significant difference was noted in the adversities encountered by school heads in television and radio-based instruction when grouped according to the trainings attended. This implies that the school heads regardless of the number of trainings they have attended encounter similar adversities in the use of television and radio as instructional mode.

a.3 Impact on the Learners' Performance

a.3.1 Sex

Table 32

Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the School Heads on the Impact of the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes on the Learners' Performance When Grouped According to Sex

School Heads Gender and Impact on Learners' Performance on the following learning modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	0.4069	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	0.0288	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	0.4640	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	0.0290	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant

Table 32 reflects the results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the school heads on the impact of the different alternative learning delivery modes on the pupils' performance when grouped according to their sex.

The results reveal a computed P-values that are less than 0.05 for modular distance learning and radio- based instruction thereby rejecting the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is significant difference in the perception of the school

heads on the impact of the modular distance learning and radio-based instruction on the learners' performance when grouped according to their gender. This implies that the perception of male and female school heads on the impact of these two learning modes on the learners' performance differ. Findings also show that the computed mean for the male school heads are higher than those of the female counterpart.

On the other hand, result of the study show no significant difference in the perception of the male and female school heads on the impact of online distance learning and television-based instruction on the learners' performance.

a.3.1 Sex

Table 33
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the School Heads on the Impact of the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes on the Learners' Performance When Grouped According to Age

School Heads Age and Respondent's on the Impact of the following learning modes on Learners' Performance	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	0.5690	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Modular Distance Learning	1.1588×10^{-06}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	0.9345	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	0.0452	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the school heads on the impact of the different alternative learning delivery modes on the learners' performance when grouped according to their age are reflected in Table 33.

It can be gleaned from the results that the P-values are less 0.05 for modular distance learning and radio-based instruction. This implies the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance which means that young and old school heads significantly differ in their perception on the impact of modular distance learning and radio-based instruction on the learners' performance. As indicated in Appendix C, the school heads who belong to the age bracket of 47-55 perceive that the modular distance learning has more impact on learners' performance, while those of age 29-37 consider the radio-based instruction to have more impact on students' learning.

On the other, no significant difference was noted in the perception of the school heads on the impact of online distance learning and television- based instruction on the learners' performance as shown by the computed P- value which is greater than 0.05 significance level.

a. 3.3 Educational Attainment

Table 34
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the School Heads on the Impact of the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes on the Learners' Performance When Grouped According to their Educational Attainment

School Heads Educational Qualification and Impact on Pupils' Performance on the following learning modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	1.5647×10^{-15}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	5.147×10^{-12}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	0.1514	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	4.7306×10^{-13}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant

Table 34 presents the results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the school heads on the impact of the different alternative learning delivery modes on the learners' performance when grouped according to their educational attainment.

The results yielded P-values which are less than 0.05 except for television based instruction. For this reason, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance which implies that there is significant difference in the perception of the school heads on the impact of online, modular distance learning, and radio-based instruction on the learners' performance when grouped according to the educational attainment. Findings further show that the school heads with masters' degree perceive that online distance learning and radio based instruction impact more on learners' performance, while the perceive modular instruction to have more impact on students' performance.

On one hand, findings show that there is no significant difference in the perception of the school heads on the impact of television-based instruction on learners' performance regardless of their educational qualification.

a. 3.4 Length of Service

Table 35
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the School Heads on the Impact of the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes on the Learners' Performance When Grouped According to Length of Service

Length of Service and respondents' Perception on the Impact of the following learning modes on Learners' Performance	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	1.4129×10^{-15}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	8.6585×10^{-11}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	0.0131	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	5.2853×10^{-19}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the school heads on the impact of the different alternative learning delivery mode on the learners' performance when grouped according to their length of service are presented in Table 35.

Data reflects a computed P-values which are less than 0.05 which led to the rejection of the null hypothesis that there is significant difference in the Perception of the school heads on the impact of the different alternative learning delivery modes on the learners' performance when grouped according to their length of service. It implies that the school heads perceive differently the impact of online, modular distance learning, television and radio-based instruction on the learners' performance when they are grouped by their number of years in the service. Findings further reveal that school heads who have served for 18-23 years perceive online distance learning to have more impact on the learners' performance, while those who have been in the service for 12-17 years consider modular distance learning and radio-based instruction to have more impact on learners' performance, and those in the service for 24 years and above consider the television based instruction to have more impact on students' performance.

a. 3.5 Position

Table 36 discloses the results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the school heads on the impact of the different alternative learning delivery modes on the learners' performance when grouped according to their position.

Table 36
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the School Heads on the Impact of the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes on the Learners' Performance When Grouped According to their Position

School Heads Position and Perception on the Impact of the following learning modes on Learners' Performance	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	1.1164×10^{-22}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	4.494×10^{-62}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	0.0007	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	1.7222×10^{-13}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant

The results show that the computed P-values are less than 0.05. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is significant difference in the perception of the school heads on the impact of the different alternative learning delivery modes on the learners' performance when grouped according to their position. It further reveals that those with Principal position perceive online distance learning and modular instruction to have more impact on pupils' performance; those with Head Teacher positions perceive the radio-based instruction to impact more on students' performance.

a. 3.6 Trainings Attended on Alternative Delivery Modes

Table 37
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the School Heads on the Impact of the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes on the Learners' Performance When Grouped According to Their Trainings Attended on Alternative Delivery Mode

School Heads Trainings on Alternative Delivery Mode and Impact on Pupils' Performance on the following learning modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	3.8713×10^{-21}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant

Modular Distance Learning	0.0039	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	0.0421	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	2.2151 x 10 ⁻²¹	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the school heads on the impact of the different alternative learning delivery modes on the learners' performance when grouped according to their trainings attended on alternative delivery mode are disclosed in Table 37.

Data reveals that the computed P- values are less than 0.05 which means the rejection of the null hypothesis rejects at 0.05 significance level. Hence, there is significant difference in the perception of the school heads on the impact of the different alternative learning delivery modes on the learners' performance when grouped according to their trainings attended on alternative delivery mode. As appended, school heads who had fewer attendance to trainings perceive the online distance learning to have more impact on learners' performance, while those who have more trainings attended consider the modular distance learning, television and radio based instruction to have more impact on learners' performance.

b. Teachers' Perception

b.1 Opportunities

b. 1.1 Gender

Table 38

Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of Teachers on the Opportunities of the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes When Grouped According to Sex

Teachers Gender and Opportunities on the following Learning Delivery Modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	0.4828	P>0.05	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Modular Distance Learning	0.4584	P>0.05	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Television-Based Instruction	0.1716	P>0.05	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	0.0581	P>0.05	Accept	Not

			H ₀	Significant
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Table 38 presents the results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the opportunities derived from the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to their sex. The results show that the computed P-values are greater than 0.05.

Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is no significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the opportunities derived from the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to their sex. It implies that the male and female teachers have similar perception on the opportunities of the online modular distance learning, television and radio-based instruction.

b.1.2 Age

Table 39
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Teachers on the Opportunities of the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes When Grouped According to Age

Teachers Age and Opportunities on the following Learning delivery Modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	0.0768	P>0.05	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Modular Distance Learning	8,699x10 ⁻¹³	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	1.0064x10 ⁻¹⁶	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	0.0343	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant

The results of the test of significance difference in the perception of teachers on the opportunities of the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to their age are presented in Table 39.

Results show a computed P-values which are less than 0.05 for modular, TV and Radio-based instruction. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance which indicates a significance difference in the perception of the teachers on the opportunities of the modular distance learning, television and radio based instruction when grouped according to their age. Findings also show that teachers in the age bracket

of 38-46 find modular distance learning to be more beneficial, while those in the 20-28 years old bracket perceive television and radio-based instruction to have more opportunities.

On the other hand, no significant difference was noted in the perception of the teachers on the opportunities of online distance learning when grouped according to their age. It implies that the teachers, regardless of their ages do not differ in their perception on the opportunities of online distance learning.

b.1.3 Educational Attainment

Table 40
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Teachers on the Opportunities of the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes When Grouped According to Their Educational Attainment

Teachers Educational Attainment and the Opportunities on the following learning modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	0.0011	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	0.0005	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	0.6405	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	0.1187	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant

Table 40 discloses the results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the opportunities of the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to their educational attainment.

The results reveal that the computed P-values are less than 0.05 for online and modular distance learning. For this reason, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance, thus, there is significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the opportunities of online and modular distance learning when grouped according to their educational attainment. As appended, teachers who are bachelors' degree holder perceive online and modular distance learning to be more beneficial.

On the other hand, no significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the opportunities of television and radio based instruction when grouped according to their educational attainment. Hence, the null hypothesis fails to reject at 0.05 significance

level. It implies that the teachers regardless of their educational attainment do not differ from each other of their perception of the opportunities of these two learning modes.

a.1.4 Length of Service

Table 41

Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Teachers on the Opportunities of the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes When Grouped According to Their Length of Service

Teachers Length of Service and Opportunities on the following Learning Delivery Modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	0.0173	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	8.0481×10^{-05}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	0.6185	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	0.0007	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant

The results of the test significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the opportunities of the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to their length of service are disclosed in Table 41.

The test of significant difference resulted to P-values that are less than 005 except for television based instruction. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance meaning there is significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the opportunities of online, modular distance learning, and radio-based instruction when grouped according to their length of service. It implies that the teachers, when clustered by their number of years in the service, differently perceive the opportunities of these three learning delivery modes when. As evidenced by the mean in Appendix C, the teachers with longer years of service consider the online, modular, and radio-based instruction to offer more opportunities.

Findings also show that there is no significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the opportunities of television-based instruction when grouped according to their length of service. This means that the teachers regardless of their number of years in the service have similar perceptions on the benefits derived from TV-based instruction.

b.1.5 Position

Table 42 exhibits the results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the opportunities of the different alternative learning delivery mode when grouped according to their position.

Table 42
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Teachers on the Opportunities of the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes When Grouped According to Their Position

Teachers Position and the Opportunities on the following learning, modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	3.1621×10^{-36}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	8.344×10^{-15}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	7.513×10^{-11}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	6.9501×10^{-28}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant

The results reveal a computed P-values which are less than 0.05. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 significance level. Therefore, there is significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the opportunities of the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to their position. It shows that Teachers 1, LSB/PSB, MT 1 and MT II perceive online, modular, television based and radio-based learning modes to be more beneficial to students' learning compared to others.

b.1.6 Trainings attended on Alternative Delivery Mode

The results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the teacher on the opportunities of the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to trainings attended on alternative delivery mode are exhibited in Table 43.

The table reflects a computed P-values that are less than 0.05 for modular distance learning and television-based instruction. For this reason, the null hypothesis rejects at 0.05 level of significance. This indicates a significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the opportunities of modular and television-based instruction when grouped according to their trainings attended on alternative delivery mode. The researcher had noted that the teachers with more attendance to trainings on alternative delivery mode perceive the modular and television based learning modes to be more beneficial to learners' learning.

Table 43
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Teachers on the Opportunities of the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes When Grouped According to Trainings Attended on Alternative Delivery

Teachers Trainings attended on Alternative Delivery Mode and Opportunities on the following Learning delivery Modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	0.5260	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Modular Distance Learning	0.0004	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	5.8375×10	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	0.1818	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant

On the other hand, no significant difference was found in the perception of the teachers on the opportunities of online distance learning and radio-based instruction when grouped according to the trainings attended on alternative delivery mode. This implies that the teachers' perception on the benefits derived from online and radio-based instruction regardless of the number of times they attended the said trainings do not differ.

Training and seminar for the implementation of the new learning modality are warranted to promote a better understanding of the new normal teaching. Hence Walsh, et.al., 188 noted that faculty trained during the emergency transition demonstrated more determination than faculty without training and faculty trained after the transition. Receiving training during the emergency transition afforded the faculty a greater cognitive ability to attend to positive behavior in the class.

b.2 Adversities

b.2.1 Gender

Table 44 reflects the results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the adversities encountered in the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to their gender.

The results reveal a computed P-values that are less than 0.05 for online distance learning and radio-based instruction. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the adversities encountered in online distance learning and radio-based instruction when

grouped according to their gender. It further shows that the perception of the male teachers on the adversities met along the said two learning modes differ from that of the female teachers. The male teachers perceive online distance learning to be more challenging while the female teachers find the radio- based instruction more challenging.

Table 44
Results of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Teachers
on the Adversities Encountered in the Different Alternative
Learning Delivery Modes When Grouped
According to Their Gender

Teachers' Gender and the Adversities Encountered on the following Learning Delivery Modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	0.0153	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	0.0881	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Television-Based Instruction	0.7711	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	0.0361	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant

On the other hand, no significant difference was noted in the perception of teachers on the adversities encountered in modular distance learning and television-based instruction when grouped according to their gender. It implies that the male and female teachers encounter similar challenges in the use of modular and TV-based delivery modes.

b.2.2 Age

Table 45
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the
Teachers on the Adversities Encountered in the Different
Alternative Learning Delivery Modes When
Grouped According to Their Age

Teachers' Age and the Adversities Encountered on the following Learning delivery Modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	0.0025	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant

Modular Distance Learning	1.7285x10 ⁻²⁵	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	0.9670	P>0.05	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	0.0234	P>0.05	Accept H ₀	Not Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the adversities encountered in the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to their age are reflected in Table 45.

It can be gleaned from the results that the computed P-values are less than 0.05 except for television based instruction. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance which means that there is significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the adversities encountered in online, modular distance learning, and radio-based instruction when grouped according to their age. As evidenced by the weighted means in Appendix C, the researcher has noted that teachers who are 56 years old and older encounter more adversities in online teaching while those of age 29-37 find the modular instruction more challenging and teachers in the age bracket 47-55 are more hard up in radio-based instruction.

There is no significant difference, however in the perception of the teachers on the adversities encountered on television-based instruction when grouped according to their age. Teachers regardless of the age bracket they belong have similar challenges encountered in TV-based instruction.

b.2.3 Educational Attainment

Table 46

Results of the of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Teachers on the Adversities Encountered in the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes When Grouped According to Their Educational Attainment

Teachers' Educational Attainment and the Adversities Encountered in the following Learning Delivery Modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	0.0011	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	6.7369x10 ⁻¹²	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant

Television-Based Instruction	6.1014x10 ⁻¹³	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	0.9265	P>0.05	Accept H ₀	Not Significant

Table 46 presents the results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the adversities encountered in the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to their educational attainment. The table reveals a computed P-values which are less than 0.05 except for radio based-instruction. This led to the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that there is significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the adversities encountered in online, modular, and television-based instruction when grouped according to their educational attainment. Results also reveal that the teachers with higher educational attainment encounter more adversities in online and modular learning modes while those with lower educational attainment are more challenged on television-based instruction.

On the other hand, teachers do not significantly differ in the adversities encountered in radio-based instruction when grouped according to their educational attainment. It implies that the teachers regardless of their educational attainment have similar challenges on the said learning modality.

b. 2.4 Length of Service

Table 47
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Teachers on the Adversities Encountered in the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes When Grouped According to Their Length of Service

Teachers Length of Service and Adversities Encountered on the following learning modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	0.0434	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	0.0007	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	0.4012	P>0.05	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	0.1823	P>0.05	Accept H ₀	Not Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the adversities encountered in the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to their length of service are presented in Table 47.

The rejection of the null hypothesis is evidenced in the computed P- values for online and modular distance learning which are less than 0.05. It shows that the teachers perceive differently the adversities of the two identified learning modalities. Teachers who have been in the service for 12- 17 years perceive more adversities in online learning while those who have served for 24 years or more are more challenged with modular instruction.

However, teacher do not significantly differ in their perception on the adversities encountered in television and radio-based instruction when grouped according to their length of service. This is shown by the computed P-values which are greater than the significance level.

b.2.5 Position

Table 48
Results of the test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Teachers on the Adversities Encountered in the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes When Grouped According to Their Position

Teachers Length of Service and Adversities Encountered on the following learning modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	$1.5651 * 10^{-26}$	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	$4.806 * 10^{-29}$	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	4.5423×10^{-14}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	4.3223×10^{-36}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant

Table 48 discloses the results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the adversities in the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to their position.

The results reveal that the P-values are less than 0.05. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the adversities encountered in the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to their position. As appended, teachers with Teachers 1 position encounter more adversities in online, television-based learning

modes, while teachers with MT 3 positions are more challenged with modular instruction, and the Master Teachers 1 are more challenged in radio- based learning instruction.

b.2.6 Trainings attended on Alternative Delivery Mode

Table 49

Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Teachers on the Adversities Encountered in the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes When Grouped According to Trainings Attended on Alternative Delivery Mode

Teachers Trainings Attended on Alternative Delivery Mode and Adversities Encountered on the following learning, modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	0.0031	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	0.0004	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	1.8538×10^{-10}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	0.1477	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the adversities encountered in the different alternative learning delivery modes when grouped according to their trainings attended on alternative delivery mode are disclosed in Table 49.

Data reflects a computed P-values that are less than 0.05 except for radio-based instruction, thus, the null hypothesis rejected at 0.05 significance level. This means that there is significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the adversities encountered in online, modular distance learning, and television-based instruction when grouped according to the trainings they have attended on alternative delivery mode. Those who attended the said training for 6-10 times encounter more adversities in online learning mode; for those who attended 11-15 times are more challenged in modular instruction; those who have attended 16 times or more have more adversities in television-based instruction.

On the other hand, there is no significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the adversities encountered on radio-based instruction when grouped according to the trainings they have attended. It implies that the teachers have experience similar adversities along the radio-based instruction regardless of the number of times they have gone for training on alternative learning modalities.

b.3 Impact on the Learners Performance
b. 3.1 Sex

Table 50
 Results of the test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Teachers on the Impact of the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes on the Learners' Performance When Grouped According to Gender

Teachers Sex and Perception on the Impact on the following learning modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	0.3063	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Modular Distance Learning	0.5465	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Television-Based Instruction	0.3127	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	0.7530	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant

Table 50 displays the results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the impact of the different alternative learning delivery modes on the learners' performance when grouped according to their sex.

The computed P-values which are greater than 0.05 significance level accepts the null hypothesis which means that there is no significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the impact of the different alternative learning delivery modes on the learners' performance when grouped according to their sex. It implies that the male and female teachers have similar perception on the impact of online, modular distance learning, television and radio-based instruction on the learners' performance.

b. 3.2 Age

The results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the impact of the different alternative learning delivery modes on learners' performance when grouped according to their age are displayed in Table 51.

It can be gleaned from the table that the computed P-values are less than 0.05. This implies the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance, hence, there is significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the impact of the different alternative learning delivery modes on learners' performance when grouped according to their age. Data further reveals teachers of age 20-28 years old consider the online learning mode to have more impact on the learners' performance, while those who belong

to the age bracket of 29-37 perceive that the modular and radio- based instruction to have more impact on the learners' performance, and the teachers aged 38-46 perceive the television- based instruction to have more impact on students' performance.

Table 51
Results of the test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Teachers on the Impact of the Different Alternative Learning Delivery on the Learners' Performance Modes When Grouped According to Age

Teachers Age and Impact on Learners' Performance on the following learning modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	0.0133	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	7.5786x10 ⁻⁶⁰	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	1.4911x10 ⁻⁰⁵	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	0.0075	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant

c. 3.3 Educational Attainment

Table 52
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Teachers on the Impact of the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes on the Learners' Performance When Grouped According to Educational Attainment

Teachers Educational Attainment and Impact on Learners' Performance on the following learning modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	0.0018	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	1.3263x10 ⁻⁵⁵	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	1.7667x10 ⁻⁰⁷	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant

Radio-Based Instruction	0.0707	P>0.05	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
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Table 52 exhibits the results of the test of significant difference in the perception of teachers on how the different alternative learning delivery modes impact on the learners' performance when grouped according to their educational attainment. The computed P-values that are less than 0.05 except for radio-based instruction reject the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the impact of online, modular distance, and television-based instruction on learners' performance when grouped according to their educational attainment. Appendix C shows that teachers with master's and bachelors' degree perceive online instruction to have more impact on learners' performance, those with MA units say that modular instruction has more impact, and those with masters' degree consider the television-based instruction more impacting on students' performance.

However, it was found out that there is no significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the impact of radio-based instruction on the learners' performance when grouped according to their educational attainment. This implies that the teachers regardless of their educational attainment have similar perception on the impact of the radio-based instruction on the learners' performance.

b. 3.4 Length of Service

Table 53
Results of the test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Teachers on the Impact of the Different Alternative Learning Delivery on the Learners' Performance Modes When Grouped According to Length of Service

Teachers Length of Service and Impact on Learners' Performance on the following learning modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	0.0015	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	0.0000	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	0.7995	P>0.05	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	0.0418	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the impact of the different alternative learning delivery modes on the learners' performance when grouped according to their length of service are exhibit in Table 53.

It can be gleaned from the results that the P-values are less than 0.05 except for television-based instruction. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the impact of the online, modular distance learning and radio-based instruction on the learners' performance when grouped according to their length of service. Data shows that teachers who have served for 0-5 years perceive online instruction to have more impact on learners' performance; those who have been teaching for 6-11 years consider the modular and radio-based instruction to have more impact on the learners' performance.

On the other hand, teachers do not significantly differ in their perception on the impact of the television-based instruction on learners' performance when grouped according to their length of service. Regardless of their length of service, they have similar perception on the impact of the television based learning mode on the learners' performance.

b. 3.5 Position

Table 54
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Teachers on the Impact of the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes on the Learners' Performance When Grouped According to their Position

Teachers' Position and Perception On the Impact of the following learning modes on Learners' Performance	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	6.1426×10^{-27}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	9.2035×10^{-31}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	1.1127×10^{-07}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	1.2329×10^{-26}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant

Table 54 reflects the results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the impact of the different alternative learning delivery mode on the learners' performance when grouped according to their position.

The results reveal a computed P-values that are less than 0.05. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance, meaning, there is significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the impact of the different alternative learning delivery modes on the learners' performance when grouped according to their position. Findings further show that Master Teachers 2 and Master teachers 3 perceive the online and modular instruction to have more impact on learners' performance, while Master Teachers 1 consider both the television and radio- based instructions to impact more on the learners' performance.

b. 3.6 Trainings Attended on Alternative Delivery Mode

Table 55
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Teachers on the Impact of the Different Alternative Learning Delivery Modes on the Learners' Performance When Grouped According to Trainings Attended

Teachers Trainings Attended on Alternative Delivery Mode and Impact on Learners' Performance on the following learning modes	Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Online Distance Learning	0.1742	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Modular Distance Learning	1.7×10^{-35}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	3.0859×10^{-06}	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	0.5244	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the impact of the different alternative learning delivery modes on the learners' performance when grouped according to the trainings attended on alternative delivery mode are reflected in Table 55.

It is evident from the results that the computed P-values are less than 0.05 except for radio-based instruction. For this reason, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance which indicate a significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the impact of online, modular distance learning, and radio-based instruction on the learners' performance when grouped according to the trainings they have attended on alternative delivery mode. As appended, the teachers who have 11-15 trainings on alternative delivery mode perceive online, modular, and the television-based instruction to have more impact on the learners' performance.

There is no significant difference though in the perception of the teachers on the impact of the radio-based instruction on the learners' performance when grouped according to their training attended on alternative delivery mode.

10. Is there a significant difference in the perception of the school heads and teachers on the different alternative delivery modalities in terms of?
a. Opportunities

Table 56
 Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the School Heads and Teachers on the Different Alternative Delivery Modalities in Terms of Opportunities

School Heads and Teacher's Perception on the Opportunities of the following ADMS	Mean		Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
	School Heads	Teachers				
Online Distance Learning	3.17	3.22	0.0647	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Modular Distance Learning	3.13	3.10	0.0015	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	3.07	3.01	0.9175	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	3.15	3.19	0.9128	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant

Table 56 presents the results of the test of significant difference in the perception of school heads and teachers on the different alternative delivery modalities in terms of opportunities.

The results show that the significance of F or P-value is less than 0.05 for modular distance learning. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance, meaning there is significant difference in the perception of school heads and teachers on opportunities derived from modular instruction. It implies that the school heads have better perception of the opportunities on the said delivery mode of learning than the teachers.

However, there is no significant difference in the perception of school heads and teachers on the opportunities derived from online distance learning, television and radio-based instructions.

b. Adversities Encountered

The results of the test of significant difference in the perception of school heads and teachers on the different alternative delivery modalities in terms of adversities encountered are presented in Table 57.

Table 57
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the School Heads and Teachers on the Different Alternative Delivery Modalities in Terms of Adversities Encountered

School Heads and Teachers' Perception on the Adversities Encountered in the following ADMS	Mean		Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
	School Heads	Teachers				
Online Distance Learning	2.74	2.68	0.1447	P>0.05	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Modular Distance Learning	3.02	3.12	0.6632	P>0.05	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Television-Based Instruction	3.05	3.15	0.5368	P>0.05	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	2.87	2.90	1.7576x10 ⁻⁵	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant

Data reveals a computed P-value that is less than 0.05 for radio-based instruction. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is significant difference in the perception of school heads and teachers on the adversities of radio-based instruction. The research further shows that the teachers encounter more adversities in radio based instruction than the school heads. This can be attributed to the fact that they are the ones directly involved in the use of RBI and are directly relating to the learners.

On the other hand, there is no significant difference in the adversities encountered by the school heads and teachers in online, modular distance learning, and television-based instruction.

c. Impact on the Learners' Performance

Table 58 discloses the results of the test of significant difference in the perception of school heads and teachers on the different alternative delivery modalities in terms of impact on the learners' performance.

It is evident from the results that the P-values is less than 0.05 for modular distance learning. For this reason, the null hypothesis rejected at 0.05 level of significance. As a result, there is significant difference in the perception of school heads and teachers on the impact of modular distance learning on the learners' performance. However, there is no significant difference in the perception of school heads and teachers on the impact of online, television and radio-based instructions on the learners' performance.

Table 58
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the School Heads and Teachers on the Different Alternative Delivery Modalities in Terms of Impact on the Learners' Performance

School Heads and Teachers Perception on the Impact of the ff: ADMs on the Learners' Performance	Mean		Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
	School Heads	Teachers				
Online Distance Learning	3.18	3.23	0.8596	P>0.05	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Modular Distance Learning	3.06	3.04	0.0006	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	2.97	2.93	0.4055	P>0.05	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	3.12	3.19	0.7429	P>0.05	Accept H ₀	Not Significant

11. The Confidence Level of the Respondents in Using the Different Learning Modalities.

Table 59
The Confidence Level of the Respondents on the Use of Online Learning Modes

Indicators	School Head		Teacher	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. I am confident to plan and prepare lessons.	3.04	Moderately Confident	3.12	Moderately Confident

2. I am confident to communicate with learners.	3.24	Moderately Confident	3.22	Moderately Confident
3. I am confident to track and monitor learners' progress.	3.12	Moderately Confident	3.12	Moderately Confident
4. I am confident where to start when it comes to online learning.	3.33	Highly Confident	3.20	Moderately Confident
5. I am confident in my teaching and learning skills.	3.10	Moderately Confident	3.22	Moderately Confident
6. I am confident in my enhanced experience in teaching.	3.20	Moderately Confident	3.37	Highly Confident
7. I am confident to efficiently manage my time.	3.20	Moderately Confident	3.33	Highly Confident
8. I am confident to improve the quality of knowledge attainment.	3.08	Moderately Confident	3.22	Moderately Confident
9. I am confident to adapt online communication techniques as a fun way to communicate with my students.	3.22	Moderately Confident	3.32	Highly Confident
10. I am confident that my viable learning approach improve quality of learning compared to conventional learning.	3.31	Highly Confident	3.13	Moderately Confident
Total	3.19	Moderately Confident	3.23	Moderately Confident

Table 59 shows the confidence level of respondents in online distance learning modality.

The data shows that school heads are **Highly Confident** of where to start when it comes to online learning and that their viable learning approach improves quality of learning compared to conventional learning while the teachers consider themselves **Moderately Confident** along these two areas.

For the other indicators, both the school heads and teachers assess themselves to be **Moderately Confident**. These include their confidence in planning and preparing lessons, communicating with learners, tracking and monitoring learners' progress, teaching and learning skills, time management, and in adapting online communication techniques as a fun way to communicate with the students.

On the average, the teachers and school heads' confidence level in online distance learning modality is **Moderate** with an overall weighted means of 3.19 and 3.23 respectively.

Table 60
The Confidence Level of the Respondents on the
Use of Modular Learning Modes

Indicators	School Head		Teacher	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. I am confident to provide clear explanations and cognizance base knowledge to students.	3.10	Moderately Confident	2.88	Moderately Confident
2. I am confident to relate new ideas to previous existing knowledge	3.15	Moderately Confident	3.01	Moderately Confident
3. I am confident in my structured balanced student workload.	3.08	Highly Confident	2.86	Moderately Confident
4. I am confident to provide opportunities for students to pursue topics in depth to understand the material for themselves.	3.02	Moderately Confident	2.86	Moderately Confident
5. I am confident to ensure an appropriate formative and comprehensive assessment strategy.	2.99	Moderately Confident	3.10	Moderately Confident
6. I am confident that the activities and exercises in modular distance learning are suited to the multiple abilities of learners.	3.05	Moderately Confident	3.11	Moderately Confident
7. I am confident that I can help learners to be capable to learn independently from the modules.	3.12	Moderately Confident	3.12	Moderately Confident
8. I am confident in checking and evaluating children's output from modules exercises.	3.12	Moderately Confident	3.20	Highly Confident
9. I am confident to know the applicable and effective	3.01	Moderately Confident	3.24	Moderately Confident

teaching approach that could be used in teaching all subjects.				
10. I am confident to provide more flexibility to distance teaching mode as well to learners.	3.22	Moderately Confident	3.15	Moderately Confident
Total	3.09	Moderately Confident	3.05	Moderately Confident

Table 60 shows the confidence level of respondents in modular distance learning modality.

Based on the results, the school heads and teachers are Moderately Confident in providing clear explanations and cognizance base knowledge to students, relating new ideas to previous existing knowledge, structuring balanced student workload and providing opportunities for students to pursue topics in depth to understand the material for themselves. They too are moderately confident of ensuring an appropriate formative and comprehensive assessment strategy, adjusting to the multiple abilities of learners, helping learners to learn independently from the modules, checking and evaluating children's output from module exercises and knowing the applicable and effective teaching approach that could be used in teaching all subjects.

This is revealed by the individual computed weighted mean and the overall weighted means of 3.09 for school heads and 3.05 for teachers. The findings of the present study is supported by Ambayon (2021) findings that modular instruction is more operative in the teaching-learning method as equated to usual teaching approaches because in this modular approach the students learn in their own stride. It is unrestricted self-learning panache in which instantaneous reinforcement, a comment is provided to practice exercise, which stimulates the students and builds curiosity in them. Hence, this kind of learning modality increases the student-centered approach in learning.

Cheng and Bakar (2017) adds that using teaching module to teach the English language as compared to the traditional method of using a textbook is meant to increase active learning and improve critical thinking, as well as problem solving skills. It gives the teacher the opportunity for conducting formative assessment in the classroom. The use of a module presents a more flexible learning environment for both instructors and learners.

The confidence level of the respondents on the use of television-based- Instruction learning modes is presented in Table 61. The data shows that the school heads **Highly Confident that TBI** leads to more effective teaching, improves confidence and credibility and increases motivation and enthusiasm for learning while the teachers are moderately confident about it.

Table 61
The Confidence Level of the Respondents on the Use of Television-Based-Instruction Learning Modes

Indicators	School Head		Teacher	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. I am confident to add a valuable real-world dimension to learning to serve as a bridge to community groups, cultural organizations, and professional and industry associations.	3.17	Moderately Confident	2.63	Moderately Confident
2. I am confident to provide greater accommodation of diverse learning styles.	2.50	Moderately Confident	3.05	Moderately Confident
3. I am confident to develop a common base of knowledge among students.	2.67	Moderately Confident	2.95	Moderately Confident
4. I am confident to make teaching more flexible, more aligned with core curricula, and more supported by other learning materials and resources	2.47	Moderately Confident	3.32	Moderately Confident
5. I am confident to create a better opportunity to increase knowledge and skills.	3.20	Moderately Confident	3.16	Moderately Confident
6. I am confident to teach more effectively.	3.33	Highly Confident	2.68	Moderately Confident
7. I am confident to improve confidence and credibility.	3.47	Highly Confident	3.00	Moderately Confident
8. I am confident to promote home-school connections, as well as bringing parents into their children's learning activities.	2.53	Moderately Confident	3.11	Moderately Confident
9. I am confident to enhance comprehension and discussion of content.	2.50	Moderately Confident	3.05	Moderately Confident

10. I am confident to increase motivation and enthusiasm for learning.	3.50	Highly Confident	2.89	Moderately Confident
Total	2.93	Moderately Confident	2.98	Moderately Confident

The table further reveals that both the school heads and teachers claim that with TBI, they are moderately confident in adding a valuable real-world dimension to learning to serve as a bridge to community groups, cultural organizations, and professional and industry associations. They also say that they are moderately confident in providing greater accommodation of diverse learning styles, developing a common base of knowledge among students, promoting home-school connections, as well as bringing parents into their children's learning activities and enhancing comprehension and discussion of content.

In terms of making teaching more flexible, more aligned with core curricula, and more supported by other learning materials and resources, the school heads find themselves Moderately Confident while the teachers are Highly Confident.

In general, the school heads and teachers are moderately confident of the use of television -based instruction as revealed by the overall weighted means of 2.93 and 2.98 respectively.

This supports what Nemine et. Al., (2021) revealed in their study that teachers have a favorable disposition towards the use of ITV and it was recommended that some television stations should broadcast well tutored and designed suitable lesson to learners.

Table 62
The Confidence Level of the Respondents on the Use of Radio-Based Learning Modes

Indicators	School Head		Teacher	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. I am confident to construct global, interactive and dynamic communications on distance education systems.	3.18	Moderately Confident	3.05	Moderately Confident
2. I am confident to develop live and taped distance programs for learner-centered education and training.	3.12	Moderately Confident	3.11	Moderately Confident

3. I am confident to create open, flexible and distributed learning environments that are carefully designed based on the framework.	3.09	Moderately Confident	3.24	Moderately Confident
4. I am confident to bridge gaps in education as it helps in improving the learning outcomes of the students.	3.15	Moderately Confident	3.32	Moderately Confident
5. I am confident to share and exchange knowledge among learners and resources.	3.14	Moderately Confident	3.21	Moderately Confident
6. I am confident to ensure that children have almost immediate access to learning opportunities despite school closures.	3.29	Highly Confident	3.17	Moderately Confident
7. I am confident to directly invite children to complete interactive exercises.	3.15	Highly Confident	3.17	Moderately Confident
8. I am confident to reduce the time and costs associated with content development and quality assurance for repurposing and adapting existing content	2.80	Moderately Confident	3.21	Moderately Confident
9. I am confident to use content repositories contain scripts, teacher guidance materials and audio file that is already proven effective	3.12	Moderately Confident	3.16	Moderately Confident
10. I am confident to use quality assurance mechanisms to improve listener engagement and learning.	3.23	Highly Confident	3.21	Moderately Confident
Total	3.13	Moderately Confident	3.18	Moderately Confident

Table 62 shows the confidence level of respondents in Radio-Based instruction as a learning modality.

The school heads and teachers say that with radio-based instruction, they are Moderately Confident to construct global, interactive and dynamic communications on distance education systems, develop live and taped distance programs for learner-

centered education and training, create open, flexible and distributed learning environments that are carefully designed based on the framework, bridge gaps in education as it helps in improving the learning outcomes of the students and share and exchange knowledge among learners and resources. They also claim that with RBI, they are Moderately Confident to directly invite children to complete interactive exercises, reduce the time and costs associated with content development and quality assurance for repurposing and adapting existing content, use content repositories contain scripts, teacher guidance materials and audio file that is already proven effective.

On the other hand, the school heads are Highly Confident to ensure that children have almost immediate access to learning opportunities despite school closures while the teachers are Moderately Confident along this line. As a whole, both the school heads and teachers have moderate confidence in to use of RBI as a learning modality as shown by their respective general weighted mean of 3.13 and 3.18.

According to Rao(1991), the use of radio in a novel way of enlivening an educational broadcast has proved attractive as a teaching method. In developing countries where a low level of education has to be remedied speedily on a large scale, the use of radio cannot be avoided. With imagination and skilled forethought this medium of mass communication can be a cornerstone on which all types of large educational programs can be mounted and carried successfully through.

Holmberg (1985) also said that strictly educational broadcasts can be used in all forms of education. As has been suggested, their use in developing countries is one of the few ways in which any real impact can be made on their large scale problem of educational provision. Educational broadcasts cannot stand on their own. But they can be usefully integrated into distance education courses and regular class meetings.

Also, Olakulehin (2021) proved that the use of instructional radio combined with lecture method promotes and enhances effective teaching-learning process. Thus, lecturers should be encouraged to use it in university education program.

12. Is there a significant difference in the confidence level of the respondents in the use of the different learning modalities?

The results of the test of significant difference in the confidence level of the respondents in the use of the different learning modalities are disclosed in Table 63.

The table shows that the computed P-values are less than 0.05 for online and modular distance instruction. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance which means that there is significant difference in the confidence level of the respondents on the use of online and modular distance learning. The findings further show that teachers are more confident in the use of online distance learning while the school heads are more confident on the use of modular distance learning.

Table 63
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Confidence
Level of the Respondents on the Use of the
Different Learning Modalities

Confidence level of the Respondents in the Use of the Following Learning Modalities	Mean		Significance of F or P-values	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
	School Heads	Teachers				
Online Distance Learning	3.19	3.23	0.0006	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	3.09	3.05	4.4924x10 ⁻⁵	P<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Television-Based Instruction	2.93	2.98	0.3761	P>0.05	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Radio-Based Instruction	3.13	3.18	0.7362	P>0.05	Accept H ₀	Not Significant

On one hand, there is no significant difference in the confidence level of the respondents in the use of television and radio based instruction. As signified by the acceptance of the null hypothesis at 0.05 significance level. It implies that the confidence level of the school heads in the use of the TBI and RBI as learning modality do not differ from that of the teachers.

Conclusions

Based from the significant findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

The use of distance learning delivery modes like online, modular, TV- based and radio-based instruction as perceived by the school heads and teachers is an opportunity for learners to learn at their own pace, having more choices about their learning materials and activities. Learners have greater flexibility in their schedule or way of learning, find more free time for interests and also allows them to conduct their learning at a time they're most likely to succeed. Further, there is more parental involvement in their children's education, and had new opportunities to learn about their children and help them learn. Teachers have access to more teaching opportunities and provides them with more opportunities to teach in a variety of ways. Through distance learning delivery modes, teachers and learners learn new technical skills.

Although there are positives to distance learning, adapting to it was quite a challenge to the learners, teachers and administrators. In the use of these distance learning delivery modes, there is absence of physical interaction, difficulty of staying motivated for those who are technologically literate, and don't help in developing oral skills and social interactions. There is also the difficulty of staying connected at all times and getting immediate feedback and requires the learners and teachers to have a good time management.

The implementation of flexible distance learning delivery modes also has its impact on learners' performance. Therefore, the four alternative delivery modes implemented in the six legislative districts in the division of Isabela are effective and acceptable for the continuance of learning in the new normal.

Further, the school heads and teachers do not significantly differ in their perception on the opportunities, adversities and impact on learners' performance of the four alternative delivery modes. Furthermore, the perception of the respondents on the opportunities, adversities, and impact of these alternative learning delivery modes on learners' performance are influenced by their age, educational attainment, length of service, training attended, and position. Moreover, the school heads and teachers have different level of confidence on the use of online distance learning and modular distance learning but have the same confidence level in the use of television-based and radio-based instruction.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are hereby presented:

1. Since the alternative delivery modes are effective and acceptable for the continuance of teaching and learning, school heads and teachers must continue adapting the alternative delivery modalities in the new normal not only during the pandemic but in cases where face to face classes are not possible.
2. The Department of Education should see to it that all school heads and teachers get more training on the use of and implementation of different alternative learning delivery modes.
3. Both school heads and teachers should continue to assess/evaluate the impact of distance learning on students' academic performance using more in depth indicators. School heads and Teachers should know the importance of developing meaningful relationships with and among students.
4. The Department of Education should find ways on how to address the issues on redefining learning. They should reflect and consider incorporating effective online learning practices to improve the different alternative learning delivery modes.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher made sure that during the conduct of the study, the following ethical concerns were followed to necessitate safe, anti-fraud, deliberate, and careful undertakings in the study:

1. The researcher, through proper communications, asked permission from the Division Office, and other concerned offices for the study;
2. The researcher also acknowledged the Department of Education and the Schools Division of Isabela for allowing her to conduct the study;
3. The researcher informed the respondents of the study through letters and a short orientation to the study. Data and information gathered were treated with utmost respect and confidentiality;
4. The researcher, properly cited gathered information and other relevant studies from authors, books, or any publications through proper citation.

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REFERENCES

- Ali, M. A. (2016). Impact of instructional radio delivery mode on academic achievement [PDF]. VFAST Journals. <https://vfast.org/journals/index.php/VTESS/article/download/232/280/879>
- Ambayon, J. (2021). Modular-based approach and students' achievement in literature. International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies, 9*(2), 92-98. <https://www.journals.aiac.org.au/index.php/ijels/article/view/6198/4380>
- Ancheta, R., & Ancheta, H. (2021). A review of modular distance learning [PDF]. World Bank Open Knowledge Repository. <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/24713>
- Anzaldo, G. (2020). Modular distance learning in the new normal education amidst COVID-19 [PDF]. ResearchGate. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/346091209>
- Arbutante, R. G. (2020, December 11). DepEd Malaybalay expands radio-based instruction (RBI) to formal education. DepEd Malaybalay. <https://www.depedmalaybalay.net/articles/deped-malaybalay-expands-radio-based-instruction-rbi-to-formal-education.html>
- Bagood, J. B. (2020). Teaching-learning modality under the new normal. Philippine Journal of Education, 99(3), 12-15.
- Calderon, J. (2006). Methods of research and thesis writing (2nd ed.). National Bookstore.

- Castroverde, F., & Acala, M. (2021). Modular distance learning modality: Challenges of teachers in teaching amid the COVID-19 pandemic. ResearchGate. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348207652>
- Cheng, C. M., & Abu Bakar, M. B. (2017). The impact of using modules in the teaching and learning of English. ResearchGate. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343684458>
- Cos, M., & Pagua, A. (2021). Factors affecting distance learning of Carrascal National High School, Division of Surigao del Sur. ResearchGate. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/352256445>
- Dangle, Y. R. P., & Sumaoang, J. D. (2021). The implementation of modular distance learning in the Philippines secondary public schools. Academia. https://www.academia.edu/49049990/Distance_Learning_Challenges_on_the_Use_of_Self_Learning_Module
- Department of Education. (2020). Adoption of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan for school year 2020-2021 in light of the COVID-19 public health emergency (DepEd Order No. 012, s. 2020). https://authdocs.deped.gov.ph/deped-order/do_s2020_012-adoption-of-the-be-lcp-sy-2020-2021/
- Elliott, V., & Lashley, L. (2017). The effectiveness of interactive radio instruction (IRI) within selected primary schools in Region Number Four. *Social Science Learning Education Journal*, 2(9), 38-47. <https://doi.org/10.15520/sslej.v2i9.38>
- Emerald, Z. (2021, October 11). Advantages and disadvantages of using television in teaching. Logical Daily. <https://logicaldaily.com/using-television-in-teaching/>
- Epstein, J. L. (2010). School/family/community partnerships: Caring for the children we share. *Phi Delta Kappan*, 92(3), 81-96. <https://doi.org/10.1177/003172171009200326>
- Esplada, J. (2010). Male teachers in the Philippines. *Philippine Daily Inquirer*. http://www.menteach.org/news/male_teachers_in_the_phillipines#:~:text=Women%2Dpo wered
- Golladay, R., Prybutok, V., & Huff, R. (2000). Critical success factors for the online learner. *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, 40(2), 69-71. <https://jite.org/documents/Vol5/v5p201-2195mart54.pdf>
- Guangul, F. M., Suhail, A. H., & Khalit, M. I. (2020). Challenges of remote assessment in higher education in the context of COVID-19: A case study of Middle East College. *Educational Assessment, Evaluation and Accountability*, 32(3), 519-535. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11092-020-09340-w>
- Halili, C. C., & Villajuan, G. S. (2021). Modular approach [PDF]. *GESS Journal*. <https://gessjournal.com/>
- Haroun, H. G. (2017). Work factors and teacher satisfaction: The mediating effect of cynicism toward educational change. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 7(1), 22-26. <https://www.iosrjournals.org/iosr-jrme/papers/Vol-7%20Issue-1/Version-4/D0701042226.pdf>
- Holmberg, B. (1985). Status and trends of distance education. Laktor Publishing.
- Information Agency. (2020). The benefits of remote learning. PIA Philippines. <https://pia.gov.ph/features/articles/1055584>
- Kwatubana, S., & Makhalemele, T. (2018). Parental involvement in education [PDF]. ResearchGate. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324820417>
- Manlove, D. C., & David, B. (1985). Flexible scheduling. Longmans Green and Company.
- Moses, P. (2016). Work factors and teacher satisfaction: The mediating effect of cynicism toward educational change. *Issues in Educational Research*, 26(2), 1-16. <https://www.iier.org.au/iier26/yim.html>
- Nemine, E. B. B., & Akinbowale, O. A. (2021). Instructional design and teaching during the pandemic [PDF]. ERIC. <https://www.ed.gov/EJ1214917.pdf>

- Olakulehin, F. K. (2021). Impact of instructional radio delivery mode on academic achievement [PDF]. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324811378>
- Paris, P. G. (2004). Online learning: A study on secondary students' attitudes towards online web-assisted learning. *International Education Journal*, 5(2), 222-235. <https://www.academia.edu/35679975>
- Rao, U. (1991). *Educational technology*. Himalaya Publishing House.
- Regalado, M. (2017). Career mobility and gender: A descriptive study of selected DepEd teachers in Iligan City. In S. Aimimtham & A. Nurmandil (Eds.), *Asia Pacific Society for Public Affairs* (pp. 55-68). Asia Pacific Society for Public Affairs. ISBN 978-602-6751-55-3.
- Sanders, D. W., & Morrison-Shetlar, A. I. (2002). Student attitudes toward web-enhanced instruction in an introductory biology course. *Journal of Research on Computing in Education*, 33(1), 251-262. <https://www.learntechlib.org/primary/p/26064>
- Savenye, W. C. (2005). Improving online courses: What is interaction and why use it? *Distance Learning*, 2(1), 1-9. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/232951239>
- Sen, V. (2021). What are the advantages and limitations of educational television? *Preserve Articles*. <https://www.preservearticles.com/education/what-are-the-advantages-and-limitations-of-educational-television/16513>
- Smart, K. L., & Cappel, J. J. (2006). Students' perceptions of online learning: A comparative study. *Journal of Information Technology Education*, 5(1), 201-215. <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/101752>
- Thomson, S. (2010). Beyond the classroom walls: Teachers' and students' perspectives on how online learning can meet the needs of gifted students. *Journal of Advanced Academics*, 21(4), 662-698. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1932202X1002100402>
- Ullah, O. (2018). Students' attitude towards online learning at tertiary level. *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324829386>
- Yu, S. (2006). Attitude toward web-based distance learning among public health nurses in Taiwan: A questionnaire survey. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 44(2), 248-256. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16253261/>